
Proof Rules for Expected Run-Times of Probabilistic Programs

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Abstract

An important characteristic of probabilistic programs is their expected run-time. While computing expected run-times of loop-free programs consists mostly of syntactic reasoning, determining the run-time of probabilistic loops is much more involved. Therefore, the question arises whether there are subclasses of loops that allow to determine their expected run-time automatically.

In this thesis we study independent and identically distributed loops (i.i.d., for short). A loop is i.i.d. whenever there is no data flow across its iterations. Using weakest pre-expectation semantics and a `wp`-style calculus for reasoning about expected run-times, we derive a proof rule to compute expected run-times of i.i.d. loops. Furthermore, we demonstrate how Bayesian Networks can be simulated by means of probabilistic programs. We show that all loops encountered in such a simulation are i.i.d. loops. Hence, our proof rule can be applied to automatically derive the expected simulation time of a given Bayesian Network.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Probabilistic programming is a powerful tool and widely applicable. On top of the standard language constructs, probabilistic programming languages allow to introduce *randomisation* into the computation by offering the possibility of sampling values from probability distributions. This provides a convenient technique to describe randomised algorithms, which exploit randomisation to solve hard problems more efficiently at the cost of tolerating a wrong solution with low probability. Moreover, there are many applications from areas like machine learning (e.g. skill rating in online games), security or ecology that can be modelled as probabilistic programs [2]. However, this list of applications is far from exhaustive. Probabilistic programming is an active field of research with rapidly increasing importance for several communities.

Freivalds' algorithm [12] is a prime example of a randomised algorithm. Suppose we are given three $n \times n$ matrices $A, B, C \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$ over the integers modulo 2. We want to verify whether C is the product of A and B , i.e. whether $AB = C$. Solving this problem by means of a simple matrix multiplication takes $\Theta(n^3)$ operations. Even the most efficient known algorithm for matrix multiplication takes roughly $\Theta(n^{2.37})$ operations [15]. Freivalds' algorithm exploits randomisation which allows for faster verification at the cost of tolerating a wrong answer with low probability. After choosing a random vector $\bar{r} = (r_1, \dots, r_n) \in \{0, 1\}^n$, it computes $B\bar{r}$, $A(B\bar{r}) = AB\bar{r}$, and $C\bar{r}$. If $AB\bar{r} \neq C\bar{r}$, then it returns " $AB \neq C$ ". Otherwise, it returns " $AB = C$ ". Hence, three matrix-vector multiplications are required which takes $\Theta(n^2)$ operations. It can be shown that the probability of the algorithm returning " $AB = C$ " when actually $AB \neq C$ holds is at most $\frac{1}{2}$. If we repeat the procedure k times, then the probability of error is at most 2^{-k} while the procedure takes $\Theta(kn^2)$ operations. This is a drastic improvement in terms of efficiency for sufficiently large n .

In contrast to non-probabilistic programs, the run-time of a probabilistic program does not only depend on the initial variable valuation but also on the probabilistic behaviour of the program. Therefore, an important characteristic of probabilistic programs is their average or *expected run-time*. While computing expected run-times of loop-free programs consists mostly of syntactic reasoning, computing expected run-times of probabilistic loops is much more involved. Deciding whether a given probabilistic program has finite expected run-time is strictly harder than solving the halting problem for ordinary non-probabilistic programs [6]. On this account, the question arises whether there are subclasses of loops that allow to compute their expected run-time *automatically*. In this thesis we study such a subclass: The so-called independent and identically distributed loops (i.i.d., for short). A loop is i.i.d. whenever there is no data flow across its iterations. For instance, the following loop adapted from [13] is independent and identically distributed:

```

i := 7;
while(i > 6){
  a0, a1, a2 :=  $\frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle$ ;
  i := 4a2 + 2a1 + a0 + 1
}

```

Figure 1.1: Simulation of a fair die.

It simulates a fair die (i.e. a uniform distribution over $\{1, \dots, 6\}$) by means of three fair coin tosses. The main contribution of this thesis is a *proof rule* to compute expected run-times of these loops. It exploits that the expected run-time of i.i.d. loops is determined by two quantities:

1. It is determined by the probability of the loop guard evaluating to true after one iteration and
2. by the expected run-time of the loop body.

In order to formally reason about these quantities, we rely on two calculi. We use *weakest pre-expectation semantics* developed by McIver and Morgan [11] to define the i.i.d. property and to reason about the probability of the guard evaluating to true after one iteration. Furthermore, we use a *wp*-style calculus developed by Kaminski et. al. [7] to reason about expected run-times. This calculus comes with several proof rules for obtaining bounds on expected run-times of loops, which will be used to prove the proof rule developed in this thesis correct.

Probabilistic programs can be used to specify a (conditional) probability distribution. Consider the following scenario: We first flip a fair coin. We then either flip the fair coin again if we observed heads, or flip a biased coin if we observed tails. This scenario can be modelled by two random variables X, Y , where X models the first coin flip (i.e. $P(X = \text{heads}) = 0.5 = P(X = \text{tails})$) and Y models the second one. Random variable Y depends on X , because we either flip a fair or a biased coin dependent on the outcome of variable X , i.e. $P(Y = \text{heads} \mid X = \text{heads}) = 0.5$ and $P(Y = \text{heads} \mid X = \text{tails}) = 0.3$. We can specify the joint distribution of X and Y by means of a probabilistic program as follows:

```

x := 0.5 · ⟨heads⟩ + 0.5 · ⟨tails⟩;    //first (fair) coin flip

if(x = heads){                          //second coin flip:
  y := 0.5 · ⟨heads⟩ + 0.5 · ⟨tails⟩}; //fair coin
if(x = tails){
  y := 0.3 · ⟨heads⟩ + 0.7 · ⟨tails⟩} //biased coin

```

Figure 1.2: Modelling a joint probability distribution.

The joint distribution of the program variables agrees with the joint distribution of the random variables. For instance, the probability of program variable x being assigned to heads *and* variable y being assigned to tails agrees with $P(X = \text{heads}, Y = \text{tails})$. In this context, independent and identically distributed loops can be applied to simulate conditioning. Sup-

pose we want to condition the value of variable x to tails. To do so, we embed that part of the program that specifies the distribution of x in a loop as shown in the following figure:

```

while( $x \neq$  tails){
   $x := 0.5 \cdot \langle$ heads $\rangle + 0.5 \cdot \langle$ tails $\rangle$ 
};

if( $x =$  heads){
   $y := 0.5 \cdot \langle$ heads $\rangle + 0.5 \cdot \langle$ tails $\rangle$ };
if( $x =$  tails){
   $y := 0.3 \cdot \langle$ heads $\rangle + 0.7 \cdot \langle$ tails $\rangle$ 
}

```

Figure 1.3: Using i.i.d. loops to simulate conditioning.

The effect of the loop is precisely to condition the value of x to tails. Thus, the probability that program variable y is assigned to heads now agrees with $P(Y = \text{heads} \mid X = \text{tails})$.

Following this idea, probabilistic programs can be used to represent probabilistic graphical models [8] such as *Bayesian Networks*. These models have a wide range of applications including speech recognition, information extraction, reliability analysis, biology and coding theory [2]. Given a finite set of (dependent) random variables, a Bayesian Network provides a compact representation of the joint distribution of these random variables. In this thesis, we formally define how to encode a distribution specified by a Bayesian Network as a probabilistic program. As demonstrated above, we use independent and identically distributed loops to simulate conditioning. Moreover, we prove that the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops can be applied to automatically compute expected run-times of probabilistic programs simulating Bayesian Networks.

Related Work There are several works dealing with formal semantics and expected run-times of probabilistic programs. Dijkstra [1] developed the predicate transformer wp in order to define *denotational semantics* for sequential non-probabilistic programs. Given a program P and a predicate over program variables F (called *postcondition*), $E = \text{wp}[P](F)$ denotes the weakest *precondition* an initial variable valuation has to satisfy such that executions of P terminate and end in a state satisfying F . Using the predicate calculus, i.e. using Boolean-valued pre- and postconditions, is insufficient to define formal semantics for sequential *probabilistic programs*. Therefore, Kozen [10] and McIver & Morgan [11] generalise Dijkstra’s predicate transformer to an *expectation transformer*. More detail on this approach is provided in Section 3.2.

Gretz et. al. [3,4] develop an *operational semantics* for probabilistic programs by means of Markov decision processes and prove it to be equivalent to the expectation transformer approach. Olmedo et. al. [5,13] extend both semantics by adding the concept of *conditioning* in probabilistic programming using *observe* statements. We do not consider those statements in this thesis, but we make use of their results that conditioning can also be realised by loops. Furthermore, they deal with independent and identically distributed *repeat...until* loops and derive their expectation transformer semantics. Since we consider *while* loops in this thesis, we adapt their work in order to characterise the semantics of independent and identically distributed *while* loops.

Kaminski et. al. develop a wp -style calculus for reasoning about expected run-times of probabilistic programs. They consider programs with loops [7] as well as recursive probabilistic programs [14] and provide several proof rules for obtaining bounds on expected run-times of loops or recursive procedures.

Kaminski and Katoen investigate the computational hardness of analysis problems for probabilistic programs [6]. In particular, they consider the computational hardness of deciding whether a probabilistic program terminates within an expected finite number of computation steps on a given input. They discover that solving this problem is strictly harder than solving the halting problem for ordinary non-probabilistic programs.

Gordon et. al. [2] point out several applications of probabilistic programming and provide an overview for the software engineering community. They depict how to encode Bayesian Networks as probabilistic programs and how to use `observe` statements to encode conditioning. We follow their idea to formally define this encoding, but use loops to realise conditioning.

Outline Chapter 2 provides the theoretical foundations we need to formally reason about probabilistic programs and their expected run-times. In Chapter 3, we present the probabilistic programming language we use throughout this thesis and introduce weakest pre-expectation semantics. Chapter 4 is dedicated to expected run-times of probabilistic programs and presents a calculus for reasoning about expected run-times. After that, we formally define the i.i.d. property and provide a characterisation of the `wp` semantics of i.i.d. loops in Chapter 5. In Chapter 6, we present the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops, apply it to an example and prove the rule sound. Finally, we formally define how Bayesian Networks can be simulated by means of probabilistic programs and prove that the proof rule can be applied to automatically compute expected run-times of probabilistic programs simulating Bayesian Networks in Chapter 7.

Chapter 2

Preliminaries

This chapter presents the mathematical foundations we need to formally reason about probabilistic programs and their expected run-times. Therefore, we describe discrete probability theory by introducing distributions, random variables and expected values. A more detailed presentation of probability theory can be found in [8].

In order to represent random experiments mathematically, a discrete probability space equips a *countable* set with a function assigning a probability, i.e. a real value in $[0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$, to each element of that set such that the sum over all probabilities equals 1.

Definition 2.1 (Discrete probability space). A *discrete probability space* (or *probability space*) is a pair (Ω, P) , where $\Omega \neq \emptyset$ is a countable set and $P : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a function satisfying

$$\sum_{\omega \in \Omega} P(\omega) = 1 . \quad \blacksquare$$

Elements of Ω are often referred to as *samples* or *outcomes*. *Sampling* from a distribution P denotes the process of randomly choosing an element $\omega \in \Omega$ with probability $P(\omega)$. If (Ω, P) is a probability space, we also refer to P as *distribution* over Ω . If Ω is clear from the context, we simply call P a distribution. We let

$$\mathcal{D}(\Omega) \triangleq \left\{ P : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1] \mid \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} P(\omega) = 1 \right\}$$

be the set of all distributions over Ω .

Remark. Most authors define discrete probability spaces by means of a triple (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) with $\mathcal{F} = 2^\Omega$ (the power set of Ω) being the set of so-called events. In this set-up, function $P : \mathcal{F} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ assigns a probability to each event. For $A \in \mathcal{F}$, value $P(A)$ denotes the probability that some element $\omega \in A$ is sampled. In this thesis it suffices to have knowledge about the probability of singleton events of the form $\{\omega\}$ for $\omega \in \Omega$. Thus we slightly adapt the definition of a discrete probability space to our needs. \blacksquare

The following example shall give an intuition on how we use discrete probability spaces to model random experiments.

Example 2.2. Imagine we are playing a game of hazard receiving a random raffle ticket indicating whether we lost, win the small price, or win the big price. Hence, the set of possible outcomes of this game is $\Omega = \{\text{lose}, \text{small_price}, \text{big_price}\}$. Furthermore, assume that $\frac{1}{2}$ of the tickets are lose tickets, with probability $\frac{3}{8}$ we win the small price, and with probability $\frac{1}{8}$ we win the big price. Then function $P : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with $P(\text{lose}) \triangleq \frac{1}{2}$, $P(\text{small_price}) \triangleq \frac{3}{8}$ and $P(\text{big_price}) \triangleq \frac{1}{8}$ is a distribution over Ω . Playing the game can be understood as sampling an element from P . \blacksquare

Given a probability space (Ω, \mathbb{P}) , it is often necessary to map the outcomes to numeric values in order to encode and infer more information about the situation one needs to model. In Example 2.2, for instance, we would like to assign the amount of money we win to each outcome of the game. Here the notion of *random variables* comes into place.

Definition 2.3 (Random variable). Let (Ω, \mathbb{P}) be a probability space. A *random variable* over (Ω, \mathbb{P}) is a function

$$X: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0}$$

assigning a non-negative real value $X(\omega)$ to each outcome $\omega \in \Omega$. ■

To understand the use of such a random variable, observe the following example.

Example 2.4. Revisit the situation from Example 2.2. We want to assign the amount of money we win to each outcome of the game. If we lose, then we receive no money. The small price is rewarded with 16 units and the big price is rewarded with 32 units. In order to describe this situation mathematically, we introduce a random variable $X: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and set $X(\text{lose}) \triangleq 0$, $X(\text{small_price}) \triangleq 16$ and $X(\text{big_price}) \triangleq 32$. ■

We are now in a position to define the *expected value* of a random variable. According to the *law of large numbers*, the expected value of a random variable X over a probability space (Ω, \mathbb{P}) is the arithmetic mean of the values we obtain, when repeatedly sampling an element $\omega \in \Omega$ from \mathbb{P} and applying it to X . Thus, if $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $(\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n) \in \Omega^n$ is an n -tuple of samples, then the arithmetic mean

$$\frac{X(\omega_1) + \dots + X(\omega_n)}{n}$$

converges to the expected value of X as n tends to infinity.

Definition 2.5 (Expected value of a random variable). Given a random variable X over a probability space (Ω, \mathbb{P}) , the *expected value* $\mathbf{E}_{\mathbb{P}}(X)$ of X is defined as

$$\mathbf{E}_{\mathbb{P}}(X) \triangleq \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \mathbb{P}(\omega) \cdot X(\omega) . \quad \blacksquare$$

The following example demonstrates the computation and the meaning of expected values.

Example 2.6. Consider the situation from Examples 2.2 and 2.4. After assigning a probability and the amount of money we receive to each outcome of the game, we are now interested in the average amount of money we would receive, if we play the game very often. For that, we have to compute the expected value of random variable X . We compute

$$\mathbf{E}_{\mathbb{P}}(X) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} \mathbb{P}(\omega) \cdot X(\omega) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0 + \frac{3}{8} \cdot 16 + \frac{1}{8} \cdot 32 = 10 .$$

Hence, we win 10 units of money on average. ■

Having the presented aspects of discrete probability theory at hand, we are now able to introduce probabilistic programs, their formal semantics and expected run-times.

Chapter 3

The Programming Language

In this chapter, we formally introduce the probabilistic programming language we use throughout this thesis as presented in [7]. It is an extension of Dijkstra's guarded command language [1]. The first section defines the set of probabilistic programs and the effect of the different language constructs. Afterwards, we introduce *weakest pre-expectation* semantics for that language as presented in [11], [3], [4], and [14].

3.1 Introduction and Syntax

On top of the standard language constructs of sequential non-probabilistic programs, a probabilistic programming language allows to introduce *randomisation* into the computation. The language we use offers this feature by means of *probabilistic assignments*. A probabilistic assignment is an assignment where the right-hand side is a *distribution expression*. For example, in the probabilistic assignment

$$i \approx \text{Unif}[1 \dots N]$$

distribution expression $\text{Unif}[1 \dots N]$ represents the uniform distribution over the set of values $\{1, \dots, N\}$, i.e. the distribution \mathbf{P} over $\{1, \dots, N\}$ with $\mathbf{P}(v) = \frac{1}{N}$ for all $v \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. Here variable i is randomly assigned to one of the values in this set, each value having equal probability $\frac{1}{N}$. We also use distribution expressions of the form

$$p_1 \cdot \langle a_1 \rangle + \dots + p_n \cdot \langle a_n \rangle$$

representing a distribution assigning probability p_j to a_j for $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Each a_j may either be a value or an arithmetic expression over the program variables.

We assume \mathbf{Var} to be the *finite* set of program variables and denote the *countable* set of possible values for these variables by \mathbf{Val} . Before defining the set of probabilistic programs, we need to clarify what a program state is and how to interpret distribution expressions and Boolean expressions over program variables in such a state.

Program states. A program state is a mapping $\sigma: \mathbf{Var} \rightarrow \mathbf{Val}$ assigning a value to each variable. We let $\Sigma = \{\sigma \mid \sigma: \mathbf{Var} \rightarrow \mathbf{Val}\}$ be the set of all program states. Given an arithmetic expression E over program variables, we let $\llbracket E \rrbracket(\sigma) \in \mathbf{Val}$ denote the evaluation of that expression in state σ . For pairwise distinct variables x_1, \dots, x_n and arithmetic expressions E_1, \dots, E_n over the program variables, we define

$$\sigma[x_1 \mapsto E_1, \dots, x_n \mapsto E_n](y) \triangleq \begin{cases} \llbracket E_1 \rrbracket(\sigma) & \text{if } x_1 = y \\ \vdots & \\ \llbracket E_n \rrbracket(\sigma) & \text{if } x_n = y \\ \sigma(y) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

as the state obtained by updating the values of x_1, \dots, x_n in σ to values $\llbracket E_1 \rrbracket(\sigma), \dots, \llbracket E_n \rrbracket(\sigma)$.

Interpretation of distribution expressions. We assume a function

$$\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket : \text{DExp} \rightarrow (\Sigma \rightarrow \mathcal{D}(\text{Val}))$$

assigning a distribution of values to each distribution expression and program state. We write $\llbracket \mu : v \rrbracket(\sigma)$ to denote the probability that distribution $\llbracket \mu \rrbracket(\sigma)$ assigns to value v .

Example 3.1. Consider the distribution expression

$$\mu = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \langle y + 1 \rangle + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \langle y + 2 \rangle$$

and a program state $\sigma \in \Sigma$ with $\sigma(y) = 1$. Then distribution $\llbracket \mu \rrbracket(\sigma)$ assigns probability $\frac{1}{3}$ to value $2 = \sigma(y) + 1$ and probability $\frac{2}{3}$ to value $3 = \sigma(y) + 2$. Hence, we have $\llbracket \mu : 2 \rrbracket(\sigma) = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\llbracket \mu : 3 \rrbracket(\sigma) = \frac{2}{3}$. ■

Interpretation of Boolean expressions. Boolean expressions over program variables are used in conditionals or loops to influence the program flow. We will also refer to them as *guards*. Depending on the program state, these expressions evaluate to one of the truth values **true** or **false**. As usual, we identify **true** with 1 and **false** with 0. For each Boolean expression φ , we assume an indicator function

$$[\varphi] : \Sigma \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$$

mapping a program state to the truth value the guard evaluates to in that state.

Example 3.2. Consider the guard $\varphi = (x < 5)$ and two program states $\sigma_1, \sigma_2 \in \Sigma$ with $\sigma_1(x) = 2$ and $\sigma_2(x) = 10$. Then $[\varphi](\sigma_1) = 1$ as $\sigma_1(x) < 5$ and $[\varphi](\sigma_2) = 0$ as $\sigma_2(x) \not< 5$. Hence, the guard φ evaluates to **true** in state σ_1 and evaluates to **false** in state σ_2 . ■

We are now in a position to formally define the set of probabilistic programs and which effect the different language constructs have on the program state.

Definition 3.3 (Set of probabilistic programs). The set of probabilistic programs **pProgs** is given by the grammar

$\mathcal{C} ::=$	empty	empty program
	skip	effectless operation
	halt	error
	$x \approx \mu$	probabilistic assignment
	$\mathcal{C}; \mathcal{C}$	sequential composition
	if (φ) $\{\mathcal{C}\}$ else $\{\mathcal{C}\}$	conditional
	while (φ) $\{\mathcal{C}\}$	while loop

where $x \in \text{Var}$, $\mu \in \text{DExp}$ and φ is a guard. ■

Note that the right-hand side of non-probabilistic assignments like $x \approx 1$ can be understood as distribution expressions representing a Dirac distribution. Dirac distributions assign probability 1 to a single point. In the case of non-probabilistic assignments we write $x := 1$ instead of $x \approx 1$.

In the following, we describe which effect the constructs have during execution. Assume program $P \in \text{pProgs}$ is in state $\sigma \in \Sigma$ before the described construct is executed. Furthermore, let $P_1, P_2 \in \text{pProgs}$, $x \in \text{Var}$, $\mu \in \text{DExp}$ and φ be a guard.

Empty program, effectless operation. Neither the statement **empty** nor the statement **skip** has an effect on the program state. The only difference lies in the underlying run-time presented in Chapter 4.

Error. The statement `halt` aborts any further execution of the program.

Probabilistic assignment. The probabilistic assignment $x := \mu$ samples a value v from distribution $\llbracket \mu \rrbracket(\sigma)$ and assigns it to x . Hence, it changes the program state to $\sigma[x \mapsto v]$ with probability $\llbracket \mu : v \rrbracket(\sigma)$ for each $v \in \mathbf{Val}$.

Sequential composition. The program $P_1; P_2$ first changes the program state according to P_1 resulting in a new state σ_1 . This state is then changed according to P_2 resulting in a new state σ_2 .

Conditional. The conditional `if (φ) $\{P_1\}$ else $\{P_2\}$` changes the program state according to P_1 if $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$, and changes the program state according to P_2 if $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$.

While loop. The while loop `while(φ) $\{P_1\}$` changes the program states according to P_1 if $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$, or terminates if $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$. This procedure is repeated until $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$ after execution of the loop body.

The language presented in [7] also allows for *probabilistic guards*. Probabilistic guards are distribution expressions over the truth values, i.e. expressions representing a distribution over $\{\mathbf{true}, \mathbf{false}\}$ or $\{0, 1\}$, respectively. They are used in probabilistic conditionals or probabilistic loops like

$$\text{if } (p \cdot \langle \mathbf{true} \rangle + (1 - p) \cdot \langle \mathbf{false} \rangle) \{P_1\} \text{ else } \{P_2\} .$$

For $p \in [0, 1]$, this program executes sub-program P_1 with probability p and executes sub-program P_2 with the remaining probability $1 - p$. As our language has to be adapted for two different calculi, we do not allow for such constructs. In fact, these constructs are syntactic sugar as we can simulate them by means of probabilistic assignments. The program from above, for example, is equivalent to the following program, where x is a fresh variable:

$$x := p \cdot \langle 1 \rangle + (1 - p) \cdot \langle 0 \rangle; \text{ if } (x = 1) \{P_1\} \text{ else } \{P_2\}$$

Instead of sampling the truth value that determines which sub-program is executed in the guard of the probabilistic conditional, we use a probabilistic assignment such that the probability that x is assigned to 1 agrees with the probability the probabilistic guard assigns to `true`. The program executes sub-program P_1 if $x = 1$, and sub-program P_2 otherwise, resulting in the same behaviour as the probabilistic conditional.

The following example gives an intuition on how `pProgs` programs look like and what they can model.

Example 3.4. Consider the following program P :

```

1  step := Unif [1 .. 10];
2  win := 0;
3  coin := 1;
4  while(coin = 1){
5    coin :=  $\frac{1}{3} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle$ ;
6    if(coin = 1){
7      win := win + step
8    } else {
9      empty
10   }
11 }
```

Program P models a game. At the beginning of the game (line 1), we sample the amount of money we win each round until the game ends and store it in variable $step$. It can be any value from $\{1, \dots, 10\}$, where each value has the same probability. In line 2, we initialize the variable storing the amount of money we won so far with 0. We then initialize variable $coin$ in line 3 such that the loop beginning in line 4 performs at least one iteration. The loop models the main part of the game: We first flip a biased coin (line 5) and store the outcome in variable $coin$. With probability $\frac{2}{3}$ we receive $step$ units of money, add this value to the amount of money we won so far (line 7), and repeat this procedure beginning in line 5 again. With probability $\frac{1}{3}$ we do nothing (line 9). In this case the guard $coin = 1$ evaluates to false, the loop terminates, and the game ends. ■

3.2 Weakest Pre-Expectation Semantics

There are several approaches to define formal semantics for an imperative probabilistic programming language like **pProgs**. In this thesis we make use of the *expectation transformer* approach developed by McIver and Morgan [11], which is a generalisation of Dijkstra's predicate transformer approach [1] for non-probabilistic programs.

Dijkstra's goal was it to define for each program P a total function $\mathbf{wp}[P](\cdot)$ between predicates over program states called *pre-* and *postconditions*. For a postcondition F , the predicate $E = \mathbf{wp}[P](F)$ denotes the weakest precondition an initial state has to satisfy such that executions beginning in such a state terminate and end in a state satisfying F [1, 4]. Consider the following non-probabilistic program as an example:

$$P : \quad \text{if}(y = 1)\{x := 2\} \text{ else } \{x := 3\}$$

A postcondition for this program might be $F = [x = 2]$. The question this postcondition models is for which initial state the program terminates in a state assigning value 2 to variable x . The predicate transformer $\mathbf{wp}[P](\cdot)$ gives an answer to this question. It maps postcondition F to the weakest precondition $E = [y = 1] = \mathbf{wp}[P](F)$. Hence, each execution beginning in a state that assigns value 1 to variable y terminates in a state assigning value 2 to variable x .

When it comes to probabilistic programs, the predicate calculus, i.e. using Boolean-valued pre- and postconditions, is insufficient as it is not possible to express probabilities that certain states will be established on termination or to express expected values of program variables. For instance, consider the program

$$P : \quad x \approx \frac{1}{3} \cdot \langle x + 1 \rangle + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \langle x + 2 \rangle$$

and postcondition $F = [x = 2]$. One needs a calculus powerful enough to express that postcondition F will be established with probability $\frac{1}{3}$ if P is executed from initial state σ with $\sigma(x) = 1$, and with probability $\frac{2}{3}$ if $\sigma(x) = 0$. Furthermore, the calculus needs to be able to express the expected value of variable x on termination. Therefore, McIver and Morgan extended Dijkstra's predicate transformer to an *expectation transformer*.

Expectations (of probabilistic programs) are random variables over program states, i.e. mappings from variable valuations to (non-negative) real numbers or infinity.

Definition 3.5 (Expectations). An expectation is a mapping

$$f : \Sigma \rightarrow [0, \infty] .$$

We let $\mathbb{E} \triangleq \{f \mid f : \Sigma \rightarrow [0, \infty]\}$ be the set of all expectations. ■

Starting with a post-expectation f that is evaluated over final states, the program text is analysed backwards, while for each statement there is a rule that transforms the expectation. Arriving at the beginning of the program, we obtain an expectation that is evaluated

over initial states and is the expected value of post-expectation f w.r.t. the distribution of final states. Formally, if $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$ and $\llbracket P \rrbracket(\sigma)$ denotes the distribution of final states obtained from executing P on initial state σ , then a post-expectation f is transformed to an expectation $\mathbf{wp}[P](f)$ such that [14]

$$\mathbf{wp}[P](f) = \lambda\sigma. \mathbf{E}_{\llbracket P \rrbracket(\sigma)}(f) .$$

We also refer to $\mathbf{wp}[P](f)$ as *pre-expectation*. Table 3.1 summarises the rules defining how each program statement transforms a given post-expectation.

P	$\mathbf{wp}[P](f)$
<code>empty</code>	f
<code>skip</code>	f
<code>halt</code>	$\mathbf{0}$
$x \approx \mu$	$\lambda\sigma. \mathbf{E}_{\llbracket \mu \rrbracket(\sigma)}(\lambda v. f[x \mapsto v](\sigma))$
$P_1; P_2$	$\mathbf{wp}[P_1](\mathbf{wp}[P_2](f))$
<code>if</code> $(\varphi) \{P_1\} else \{P_2\}$	$[\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P_1](f) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P_2](f)$
<code>while</code> $(\varphi) \{P'\}$	$\mathbf{lfp} g. ([\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P'](g) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f)$

Table 3.1: Rules for defining the expectation transformer \mathbf{wp} . Here μ is a distribution expression, φ is a guard, and \mathbf{lfp} denotes the least fixed point operator w.r.t. ordering \preceq on expectations, which is explained below.

In order to understand the different rules, we need to introduce some notation. We use boldface for constant expectations, e.g. $\mathbf{1} \triangleq \lambda\sigma. 1$. Given an arithmetic expression E over the program variables, we write E for the expectation that on state σ returns $\llbracket E \rrbracket(\sigma)$, e.g. for $x, y \in \mathbf{Var}$, we have $f = x + y \triangleq \lambda\sigma. \sigma(x) + \sigma(y)$. We also define $f[x_1 \mapsto E_1, \dots, x_n \mapsto E_n](\sigma) \triangleq f(\sigma[x_1 \mapsto E_1, \dots, x_n \mapsto E_n])$ for the sake of readability. Equality and ordering \preceq between expectations is defined point-wise, i.e. for $f, g \in \mathbb{E}$

- $f = g$ iff $f(\sigma) = g(\sigma)$ for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$, and
- $f \preceq g$ iff $f(\sigma) \leq g(\sigma)$ for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$.

Arithmetic operations between expectations or between (non-negative) constants and expectations are also defined point-wise: That is to say, for $a \in \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0}$, $g, f \in \mathbb{E}$ and $\bowtie \in \{+, \cdot\}$, we define

- $a \bowtie f \triangleq \lambda\sigma. a \bowtie f(\sigma)$, and
- $f \bowtie g \triangleq \lambda\sigma. f(\sigma) \bowtie g(\sigma)$.

We are now in a position to explain the rules for each construct.

Empty program, effectless operation. Neither the statement `empty` nor the statement `skip` has an effect on the distribution of final states and therefore does not transform the expectation.

Error. Statement `halt` transforms every expectation to the constantly zero expectation.

Probabilistic assignment. The way a probabilistic assignment $x \approx \mu$ transforms the expectation is more involved. By considering Definition 2.5, the rule can be recast to

$$\mathbf{wp}[x \approx \mu](f) = \lambda\sigma. \sum_{v \in \mathbf{Val}} \llbracket \mu : v \rrbracket(\sigma) \cdot f[x \mapsto v](\sigma) .$$

Hence, we obtain an expectation that on state σ returns the sum over all values v , where each addend is of the form $f[x \mapsto v](\sigma)$, weighted with probability $\llbracket \mu : v \rrbracket(\sigma)$, i.e. the probability that x is assigned to value v on state σ . The following example emphasizes the usage of the notation $f[x \mapsto E]$, which denotes the syntactic replacement of x by E in f .

Example 3.6. Consider the probabilistic assignment

$$P : x \approx \frac{1}{3} \cdot \langle x + 1 \rangle + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \langle x + 2 \rangle .$$

By making use of the notation $f[x \mapsto E]$, the transformed post-expectation looks as follows:

$$\text{wp}[P](f) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot f[x \mapsto x + 1] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot f[x \mapsto x + 2]$$

Note that by letting $f := x$, pre-expectation $\text{wp}[P](x)(\sigma)$ returns the expected value of variable x on termination when beginning in initial state σ , because we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P](x) &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot (x + 1) + \frac{2}{3} \cdot (x + 2) \\ &= \lambda\sigma. \frac{1}{3} \cdot (\sigma(x) + 1) + \frac{2}{3} \cdot (\sigma(x) + 2) . \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Sequential composition. The rule for determining the pre-expectation of two sequentially composed programs underlines the fact that we analyse the program backwards in order to obtain the pre-expectation of the whole program. In order to compute the pre-expectation of a construct $P_1; P_2$, we first compute the pre-expectation $\text{wp}[P_2](f)$ and proceed using that intermediate expectation to compute $\text{wp}[P_1](\text{wp}[P_2](f))$.

Example 3.7. Observe the following program $P \in \text{pProgs}$ consisting of a non-probabilistic and a probabilistic assignment:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 : x &:= 1; \\ P_2 : x &\approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle x + 1 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle x + 2 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

In order to compute the pre-expectation $\text{wp}[P](x)$, we first compute $\text{wp}[P_2](x) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 1) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 2)$ and then proceed by computing

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P](f) &= \text{wp}[P_1](\text{wp}[P_2](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_1]\left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 1) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 2)\right) \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 1) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x + 2)\right)[x \mapsto 1] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot 2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 3 = 2.5 . \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Conditional. The pre-expectation $\text{wp}[\text{if } (\varphi) \{P_1\} \text{ else } \{P_2\}](f)$ of a conditional returns pre-expectation $\text{wp}[P_1](f)(\sigma)$ on each state σ satisfying the guard (i.e. $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$), and returns pre-expectation $\text{wp}[P_2](f)(\sigma')$ on each state that does not satisfy the guard (i.e. $[\neg\varphi](\sigma') = 1$). Note that as $[\varphi]$ and $[\neg\varphi]$ can be viewed as $\{0, 1\}$ -valued expectations, the pre-expectation of a conditional remains a mapping from program states to non-negative real numbers.

Example 3.8. Consider the following program $P \in \text{pProgs}$:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{if}(x = 1)\{ \\ P_1 : & \quad y := \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 2 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 4 \rangle \\ & \quad \} \text{ else } \{ \\ P_2 : & \quad y := \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 6 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 8 \rangle \} \end{aligned}$$

Assume we want to compute the expectation that on initial state σ returns the expected value of variable y on termination, i.e. $\text{wp}[P](y)$. Therefore, we first compute expectations $\text{wp}[P_1](y) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 4 = 3$ and $\text{wp}[P_2](y) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 8 = 7$. We then proceed by using the rule for conditionals and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P](y) &= [x = 1] \cdot \text{wp}[P_1](y) + [x \neq 1] \cdot \text{wp}[P_2](y) \\ &= [x = 1] \cdot 3 + [x \neq 1] \cdot 7 . \end{aligned}$$

This agrees with the intuition: Each initial state σ with $\sigma(x) = 1$ causes the execution of P_1 and hence $\text{wp}[P](y)(\sigma) = 3$. On the other hand, each initial state σ' with $\sigma(x) \neq 1$ causes the execution of P_2 , hence $\text{wp}[P](y)(\sigma') = 7$. \blacksquare

While loop. While the pre-expectation of the other constructs can be obtained by means of syntactic reasoning, determining the pre-expectation $\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P'\}](f)$ of a loop requires the computation of the least fixed point of function $\lambda g. [\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P'](g) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f$. Chapter 5 provides a theorem that helps to infer the fixed point for the class of i.i.d. loops.

The following theorem summarises the results from [3, pp. 27-28]. Given a function Φ , we let Φ^k denote the k -fold application of Φ .

Theorem 3.9. *Let $P \in \text{pProgs}$, φ be a guard and $f \in \mathbb{E}$. Then function $\Phi(g) = [\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P](g) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f$ has a least fixed point which is given by*

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Phi^n(\mathbf{0}) = \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f) .$$

The first observation following from this theorem is that the expectation transformer $\text{wp}[\cdot]$ is well-defined for all $P \in \text{pProgs}$, since the pre-expectation of every loop exists. Furthermore, it gives rise to a method that might help finding the pre-expectation $\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)$ of a loop: Starting with the computation of $\Phi(\mathbf{0})$, we perform a fixed point iteration and compute $\Phi^2 = \Phi(\Phi(\mathbf{0}))$, $\Phi^3 = \Phi(\Phi(\Phi(\mathbf{0})))$, \dots , trying to deduce a pattern for $\Phi^n(\mathbf{0})$. Once such a pattern is found it might be easier to compute $\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Phi^n(\mathbf{0})$. We demonstrate this method in the following example.

Example 3.10. Consider program P from Example 3.4:

```

1  step  $\approx$  Unif[1...10];
2  win := 0;
3  coin := 1;
4  while(coin = 1){
5    coin  $\approx$   $\frac{1}{3} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle$ ;
6    if(coin = 1){
7      win := win + step
8    } else {
9      empty
10   }
11 }
```

We are interested in an upper bound on the expected amount of money we win, i.e. in an upper bound on the expected value of variable win . Hence, we have to compute an upper bound on $\text{wp}[P](win)$. Let P_1, P_2, P_3 denote the probabilistic assignments in line 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Furthermore, let P_{while} denote the loop beginning in line 4 and let P_{body} denote its body, i.e. the program from lines 5 to 10. Hence, we have

$$\text{wp}[P](win) = \text{wp}[P_1; P_2; P_3; P_{\text{while}}](win) .$$

Following the rule for sequential composition, we first need to compute an upper bound on $\text{wp}[P_{\text{while}}](win)$. Therefore, we have to find the least fixed point of function

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(g) &= [coin = 1] \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](g) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot g[coin \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot g[coin \mapsto 1, win \mapsto win + step] \right) \\ &\quad + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win .\end{aligned}$$

As described above, we perform a fixed point iteration to deduce a pattern for $\Phi(\mathbf{0})^n$:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(\mathbf{0}) &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot \mathbf{0}[coin \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \mathbf{0}[coin \mapsto 1, win \mapsto win + step] \right) \\ &\quad + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ &= [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ \Phi^2(\mathbf{0}) &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot win \right) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ \Phi^3(\mathbf{0}) &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot win + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot (win + step) \right) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ \Phi^4(\mathbf{0}) &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot win + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot (win + step) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot (win + 2 \cdot step) \right) \right) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot win + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot (win + step) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot (win + 2 \cdot step) \right) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ &\quad \vdots \\ \Phi^{n+2} &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^i \cdot (win + i \cdot step) \right) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ &\quad \vdots \\ \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Phi^n(\mathbf{0}) &= [coin = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^i \cdot (win + i \cdot step) \right) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win \\ &= [coin = 1] \cdot (win + 2 \cdot step) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win\end{aligned}$$

After performing 4 fixed point iterations we are able to deduce a pattern for $\Phi^{n+2}(\mathbf{0})$, which allows us to express $\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \Phi^n(\mathbf{0})$ by means of an infinite series. The closed form of the series was computed by using a computer algebra system. Hence, we propose

$$\text{wp}[P_{\text{while}}](win) \leq [coin = 1] \cdot (win + 2 \cdot step) + [coin \neq 1] \cdot win . \quad (3.I)$$

In order to prove Equation 3.I, we need to check whether the right-hand side is indeed a fixed point of Φ , because every fixed point of Φ is an upper bound on the *least* fixed point of Φ .

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Phi ([\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win}) \\
&= [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot ([\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win}) [\text{coin} \mapsto 0] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{2}{3} \cdot ([\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win}) [\text{coin} \mapsto 1, \text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}] \right) \\
&\quad + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win} \\
&= [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot \text{win} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot (\text{win} + 3 \cdot \text{step}) \right) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win} \\
&= [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{3} \cdot \text{win} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \text{win} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 3 \cdot \text{step} \right) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win} \\
&= [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win} .
\end{aligned}$$

Having determined an upper bound on the pre-expectation of loop P_{while} , we can proceed with the computation of $\text{wp}[P](\text{win})$ by applying the rules for sequential composition and probabilistic assignment:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{wp}[P](\text{win}) &= \text{wp}[P_1; P_2; P_3; P_{\text{while}}](\text{win}) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1; P_2; P_3](\text{wp}[P_{\text{while}}](\text{win})) \\
&\leq \text{wp}[P_1; P_2; P_3]([\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win}) \\
&\quad \text{(By Equation 3.I and monotonicity of wp (see Lemma 3.11))} \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1; P_2](\text{wp}[P_3]([\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win})) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1; P_2]([\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \text{win}) [\text{coin} \mapsto 1]) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1; P_2](\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step}) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1](\text{wp}[P_2](\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step})) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1]((\text{win} + 2 \cdot \text{step})[\text{win} \mapsto 0]) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1](2 \cdot \text{step}) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{10} \frac{1}{10} \cdot (2 \cdot \text{step})[\text{step} \mapsto i] \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{10} \frac{1}{10} \cdot (2 \cdot i) = 11
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we win at most 11 units of money on average when playing the game modelled by program P . ■

Finally, the following lemma summarises the algebraic properties of the transformer wp we make use of in the remainder of this thesis.

Lemma 3.11 (Basic properties of wp [11, 14]). *For all $P \in \text{pProgs}$, expectations $f_1, f_2 \in \mathbb{E}$ and scalars $a_1, a_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0}$ the following holds:*

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Linearity:} & \quad \text{wp}[P](a_1 \cdot f_1 + a_2 \cdot f_2) = a_1 \cdot \text{wp}[P](f_1) + a_2 \cdot \text{wp}[P](f_2) \\
\text{Preservation of } \mathbf{0}: & \quad \text{wp}[P](\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0} \\
\text{Monotonicity:} & \quad f_1 \preceq f_2 \implies \text{wp}[P](f_1) \preceq \text{wp}[P](f_2)
\end{aligned}$$

Chapter 4

A Calculus of Expected Run-Times

In this chapter, we first give an introduction to expected run-times of probabilistic programs. Afterwards, we present a calculus of expected run-times together with the run-time model of the presented programming language. The last section depicts a family of proof rules to establish both upper and lower bounds on the expected run-time of loops, which will be used in the following chapters to prove the proof rule developed in this thesis correct. The calculus, the run-time model, and the proof rules follow the presentation in [7].

4.1 Expected Run-Times

The execution of non-probabilistic programs from a fixed initial state will always result in the same run-time. Consider the following non-probabilistic program P as an example:

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{if}(x = 1)\{ \\ P_1 : \quad \text{skip}; \text{skip} \\ \} \text{ else } \{ \\ P_2 : \quad \text{skip} \\ \} \end{array}$$

Assume the evaluation of a guard and the execution of a `skip` statement cost 1 unit of time each. Then each execution from initial state σ with $\sigma(x) = 1$ costs 3 units of time, while executions beginning in a state σ' with $\sigma'(x) \neq 1$ cost 2 units of time. As the run-time of P only depends on the initial state, we could define a mapping $\mathsf{T}_P: \Sigma \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ such that $\mathsf{T}_P(\sigma)$ denotes the run-time of P when executed on initial state σ .

In general, it is not possible to define such a mapping for probabilistic programs as the run-time of those programs does not only depend on the initial state, but also on the probabilistic behaviour. Observe the probabilistic program P' shown in Figure 4.1 as an example: The run-time of P' does not only depend on the initial state σ , but also on the value of x sampled at the beginning of the program. Suppose a probabilistic assignment costs 1 unit of time. With probability $\frac{1}{2}$ variable x is assigned to 1, which causes the execution of P'_2 and a run-time of 4 or 5, respectively, depending on $\sigma(y)$. On the other hand, with probability $\frac{1}{2}$ variable x is assigned to 2, which causes the execution of P'_3 and a run-time of 3.

If we fix an initial state σ , the run-time of a probabilistic program can be viewed as a random variable, mapping each possible run to a run-time, each run having a certain probability. The *expected run-time* of P' is the expected value of that random variable, i.e. the average amount of time executions of P' cost when beginning in state σ . Fixing initial state σ with $\sigma(y) = 1$ in the example above, we have two possible runs: One run costs 4 units of time and occurs with probability $\frac{1}{2}$. The other run costs 3 units of time and occurs with

$$\begin{array}{l}
P'_1 : x \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 2 \rangle; \\
\quad \text{if}(x = 1)\{ \\
P'_2 : \quad \text{if}(y = 1) \{\text{skip}\} \text{ else } \{\text{skip}; \text{skip}\} \\
\quad \quad \quad \} \text{ else } \{ \\
P'_3 : \quad \text{skip} \\
\quad \quad \quad \}
\end{array}$$
Figure 4.1: Example program P' .

probability $\frac{1}{2}$. Hence, the execution of P' beginning in state σ costs $\frac{1}{2} \cdot 4 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 3 = 3.5$ units of time on average.

Having understood what we mean by expected run-time, we are now in a position to introduce the calculus.

4.2 A Calculus of Expected Run-Times

In the last subsection, we computed the expected run-time of a probabilistic program by means of informally describing the possible runs, their costs and probabilities. In this subsection, we present a calculus allowing us to *formally* reason about expected run-times of probabilistic programs.

The goal of Kaminski et. al. [7] is to define a function for each program P mapping each initial state σ to the expected run-time of P . Hence, such a function f is of type $\Sigma \rightarrow [0, \infty]$, i.e. a mapping from program states to non-negative real values or infinity. We let

$$\mathbb{T} \triangleq \{f \mid f: \Sigma \rightarrow [0, \infty]\}$$

be the function space of run-times. Observe that the function space of run-times \mathbb{T} and the set of all expectations \mathbb{E} coincide. Therefore, we use the same notation as for expectations, i.e. $f[x \mapsto E]$, boldface for constant run-times and point-wise defined equality, ordering \preceq and arithmetic operations.

In order to define the expected run-time of a program, they define a run-time transformer

$$\text{ert}[\cdot]: \text{pProgs} \rightarrow (\mathbb{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{T})$$

such that $\text{ert}[P](f)(\sigma)$ gives the expected run-time of program $P \in \text{pProgs}$ starting in initial state $\sigma \in \Sigma$, if $f \in \mathbb{T}$ captures the run-time of the computation following P . In this context, we refer to f as *continuation*. By instantiating continuation f with the constantly zero run-time, $\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$ gives the expected run-time of P .

As the ert transformer is a quantitative variant of Dijkstra's wp transformer, it works in a similar way: We determine the expected run-time of a program by starting with the constantly zero run-time $\mathbf{0}$ and analyse the program backwards, while for each program statement there is a rule that transforms the run-time. Arriving at the beginning of the program we obtain a run-time $f \in \mathbb{T}$ that returns the expected run-time of the program on each initial state σ . Table 4.1 summarizes the rules defining how a given run-time is transformed by each statement.

P	$\text{ert}[P](f)$
empty	f
skip	$\mathbf{1} + f$
halt	$\mathbf{0}$
$x := \mu$	$\mathbf{1} + \lambda\sigma. \mathbf{E}_{[\mu](\sigma)}(\lambda v. f[x \mapsto v](\sigma))$
$P_1; P_2$	$\text{ert}[P_1](\text{ert}[P_2](f))$
if $(\varphi) \{P_1\}$ else $\{P_2\}$	$\mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P_1](f) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P_2](f)$
while $(\varphi) \{P'\}$	$\text{lfp } X. (\mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P'](X) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f)$

Table 4.1: Rules for defining the run-time transformer ert . Here μ is a distribution expression, φ is a guard, and lfp denotes the least fixed point operator w.r.t. ordering \preceq on run-times.

The definition of the ert transformer also determines the run-time model of **pProgs**. In the following, we describe the run-time model in detail by explaining how each statement transforms a given run-time.

Empty program. The execution of the statement **empty** costs no time. Hence, continuation f is not transformed by ert , because there are no costs to add.

Effectless operation. Executing the **skip** statement costs 1 unit of time. Thus, if $f \in \mathbb{T}$ captures the expected run-time of the computation following the **skip** statement, then the computation including the statement costs $\mathbf{1} + f$ units of time.

Error. As the statement **halt** aborts any further execution, every continuation is transformed to the constantly zero run-time.

Sequential composition. The rule for sequentially composed programs suggests that we analyse the program backwards in order to obtain the expected run-time of the whole program. To compute the run-time of $P_1; P_2$ w.r.t. continuation f , we first compute $\text{ert}[P_2](f)$. We then use that run-time as a new continuation and compute $\text{ert}[P_1](\text{ert}[P_2](f))$.

Probabilistic assignment. The rule for probabilistic assignments is more involved. By considering Definition 2.5, the rule can be recast to

$$\text{ert}[x := \mu](f) = \mathbf{1} + \lambda\sigma. \sum_{v \in \text{Val}} [\mu : v](\sigma) \cdot f[x \mapsto v](\sigma).$$

Executing a probabilistic assignment costs 1 unit of time. So if f captures the expected run-time of the computation following the probabilistic assignment, we obtain the expected run-time of the computation including the assignment by adding the constant run-time $\mathbf{1}$ to the sum of the run-time of each possible subsequent computation, weighted according to their probabilities.

Conditional. The evaluation of a guard costs 1 unit of time. Hence, we obtain the expected run-time of a conditional if $(\varphi) \{P_1\}$ else $\{P_2\}$ by adding the constant run-time $\mathbf{1}$ to the run-time that either returns $\text{ert}[P_1](f)(\sigma)$ if state σ satisfies the guard (i.e. $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$), or returns $\text{ert}[P_2](f)(\sigma)$ if state σ does not satisfy the guard (i.e. $[\neg\varphi](\sigma) = 1$).

The following example shall demonstrate the rules for the constructs explained so far and how to determine the expected run-time of a given loop-free program.

Example 4.1. Revisit program P' from Figure 4.1:

$$\begin{aligned}
P'_1 &: x \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 2 \rangle; \\
&\quad \text{if}(x = 1)\{ \\
P'_2 &: \quad \text{if}(y = 1) \{\text{skip}\} \text{else} \{\text{skip}; \text{skip}\} \\
&\quad \quad \quad \} \text{else} \{ \\
P'_3 &: \quad \quad \quad \text{skip} \\
&\quad \quad \quad \}
\end{aligned}$$

We want to verify that executions starting in a state assigning 1 to variable y cost indeed 3.5 units of time on average. Therefore, we have to determine $\text{ert}[P'](\mathbf{0}) = \text{ert}[P'_1; \text{if}(x = 1) \{P'_2\} \text{else} \{P'_3\}](\mathbf{0})$. We compute

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{ert}[P'_2](\mathbf{0}) &= \text{ert}[\text{if}(y = 1) \{\text{skip}\} \text{else} \{\text{skip}; \text{skip}\}](\mathbf{0}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \text{ert}[\text{skip}](\mathbf{0}) + [y \neq 1] \cdot \text{ert}[\text{skip}; \text{skip}](\mathbf{0}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{0}) + [y \neq 1] \cdot \text{ert}[\text{skip}](\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{0}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1} + \mathbf{0}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{2}
\end{aligned}$$

and $\text{ert}[P'_3](\mathbf{0}) = \text{ert}[\text{skip}](\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{1}$. Having computed the run-time of sub-programs P'_2 and P'_3 , we proceed:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{ert}[P'](\mathbf{0}) &= \text{ert}[P'_1; \text{if}(x = 1) \{P'_2\} \text{else} \{P'_3\}](\mathbf{0}) \\
&= \text{ert}[P'_1](\text{ert}[\text{if}(x = 1) \{P'_2\} \text{else} \{P'_3\}](\mathbf{0})) \\
&= \text{ert}[P'_1](\mathbf{1} + [x = 1] \cdot \text{ert}[P'_2](\mathbf{0}) + [x \neq 1] \cdot \text{ert}[P'_3](\mathbf{0})) \\
&= \text{ert}[P'_1](\mathbf{1} + [x = 1] \cdot (\mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{2}) + [x \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{1}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + [x = 1] \cdot (\mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{2}) + [x \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{1}) [x \mapsto 1] \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + [x = 1] \cdot (\mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{2}) + [x \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{1}) [x \mapsto 2] \\
&= \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{2}) + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{2} + [y = 1] \cdot \mathbf{1} + [y \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{2}) + \mathbf{1}
\end{aligned}$$

Let $\sigma \in \Sigma$ with $\sigma(y) = 1$. We then have

$$\text{ert}[P'](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) = \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\mathbf{2} + \underbrace{[y = 1](\sigma)}_{=1} \cdot \mathbf{1} + \underbrace{[y \neq 1](\sigma)}_{=0} \cdot \mathbf{2}) + \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \mathbf{3} + \mathbf{1} = 3.5,$$

which verifies what we have proposed. ■

While loop. The evaluation of a loop guard costs 1 unit of time. When it comes to analysing the expected run-time of loops, the situation is similar to the determination of the pre-expectation of a loop. Expected run-times of loop-free programs can be computed mostly by means of syntactic reasoning. Determining the run-time of a loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ w.r.t. continuation f requires the computation of the least fixed point of function $F_f(X) = \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](X) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f$. As the least fixed point of function F_f exists for every guard φ , program P , and continuation $f \in \mathbb{T}$, the ert transformer is well-defined [7, p. 9]. We use function F_f frequently in this thesis and therefore define:

Definition 4.2 (Characteristic functional of a loop [7, p. 9]). Let $P \in \text{pProgs}$, φ be a guard and $f \in \mathbb{T}$. We call

$$F_f^{(\varphi, P)} : \mathbb{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{T}, X \mapsto \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](X) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f$$

the *characteristic functional* of loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ w.r.t. continuation f . ■

In the next section, we present a family of proof rules to establish both upper and lower bounds for expected run-times of loops.

4.3 Proof Rules for Expected Run-Times of Loops

The proof rules build on the notion of so-called ω -invariants. In order to understand that notion, observe that the ordering \succeq on run-times is also defined point-wise, i.e. given $f, g \in \mathbb{T}$, $f \succeq g$ iff $f(\sigma) \geq g(\sigma)$ for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$.

Definition 4.3 (ω -invariants [7]). Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$, φ be a guard and $f \in \mathbb{T}$. Moreover let $I_n \in \mathbb{T}$ be a run-time parametrised by $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We say that I_n is a lower ω -invariant of loop $\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ with respect to f iff

$$F_f^{(\varphi, P)}(\mathbf{0}) \succeq I_0 \quad \text{and} \quad F_f^{(\varphi, P)}(I_n) \succeq I_{n+1} \quad \text{for all } n \geq 0 .$$

Dually, we say that I_n is an upper ω -invariant iff

$$F_f^{(\varphi, P)}(\mathbf{0}) \preceq I_0 \quad \text{and} \quad F_f^{(\varphi, P)}(I_n) \preceq I_{n+1} \quad \text{for all } n \geq 0 . \quad \blacksquare$$

The following theorem states that the asymptotic behaviour of I_n yields a lower (resp. upper) bound on the expected run-time of the entire loop.

Theorem 4.4 (Bounds from ω -invariants [7]). Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$, φ be a guard and $f \in \mathbb{T}$.

1. If I_n is a lower ω -invariant of loop $\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ with respect to f and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n$ exists¹, then

$$\text{ert}[\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f) \succeq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n .$$

2. If I_n is an upper ω -invariant of loop $\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ with respect to f and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n$ exists, then

$$\text{ert}[\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f) \preceq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n .$$

Note that if I_n is both a lower and upper ω -invariant and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n$ exists, then $\text{ert}[\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n$.

The following example demonstrates how to determine a parametrised run-time I_n such that it is both a lower and upper ω -invariant and how to apply Theorem 4.4 to obtain the expected run-time of a given loop.

Example 4.5. Reconsider program P from Example 3.4:

```

1  step := Unif [1 .. 10];
2  win := 0;
3  coin := 1;
4  while(coin = 1){
5    coin :=  $\frac{1}{3} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle$ ;
6    if(coin = 1){
7      win := win + step
8    } else {
9      empty
10   }
11 }
```

¹Limit $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n$ is to be understood point-wise on $\mathbb{R}^{\geq 0} \cup \{\infty\}$, i.e. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n = \lambda\sigma. \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\sigma)$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\sigma) = \infty$ is considered a valid value.

We want to determine the expected run-time of the loop beginning in line 4 w.r.t. continuation $\mathbf{0}$. Let P_{while} denote the loop and P_{body} the loop body. First of all, we compute $\text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](X)$ to obtain the characteristic functional of loop P_{while} :

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](X) \\
&= \text{ert}[\text{coin} \approx \dots; \text{if } (\text{coin} = 1) \{ \text{win} := \dots \} \text{ else } \{ \text{empty} \}](X) \\
&= \text{ert}[\text{coin} \approx \dots] (\mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot (\mathbf{1} + X[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}]) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot X) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + X[\text{coin} \mapsto 0]) + \frac{2}{3} \cdot (\mathbf{2} + X[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1]) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{4}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot X[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot X[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1] \\
&= \frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot X[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot X[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1]
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, for the characteristic functional F_0 of loop P_{while} w.r.t. continuation $\mathbf{0}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0(X) &= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](X) + [\text{coin} \neq 1] \cdot \mathbf{0} \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot X[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot X[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1] \right).
\end{aligned}$$

As we want to find a parametrised run-time I_n that is *both* a lower and upper ω -invariant, run-time I_n has to satisfy $F_0(\mathbf{0}) = I_0$ and $F_0(I_n) = I_{n+1}$. We perform a fixed point iteration by computing $F_0(\mathbf{0}) =: I_0$, $F_0(F_0(\mathbf{0})) = F_0^2(\mathbf{0}) =: I_1, \dots$ and deduce a pattern for I_n :

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0(\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \mathbf{0}[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \mathbf{0}[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \frac{8}{3} =: I_0
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0^2(\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot I_0[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot I_0[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{3}}_{=1-2/3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} + \frac{8}{3} \right) \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} + \frac{8}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} \right) =: I_1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0^3(\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot I_1[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot I_1[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1} + \frac{8}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} \right) \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{3}}_{=1-2/3} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{8}{3} \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{8}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{8}{3} \right) =: I_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0^4(\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot I_2[\text{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot I_2[\text{win} \mapsto \text{win} + \text{step}, \text{coin} \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\text{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{1} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{8}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{8}{3} \right) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{3}}_{=1-2/3} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{2}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{8}{3} \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\underbrace{1 + \frac{2}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2}_{=\sum_{i=0}^2 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i} + \underbrace{\frac{8}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{8}{3} + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^3 \cdot \frac{8}{3}}_{=\frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^3 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i} \right) =: I_3 \\
&\quad \vdots \\
F_{\mathbf{0}}^{n-1}(\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) =: I_n .
\end{aligned}$$

After performing 4 fixed point iterations, we propose I_n as a lower and upper ω -invariant of loop $P_{\textit{while}}$ w.r.t. continuation $\mathbf{0}$. In order to verify this proposition, we have to show

1. $F_{\mathbf{0}}(\mathbf{0}) = I_0$ and

2. $F_{\mathbf{0}}(I_n) = I_{n+1}$.

Proof of 1. We have

$$F_{\mathbf{0}}(\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \frac{8}{3} = \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^0 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{-1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) = I_0 .$$

Proof of 2. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{\mathbf{0}}(I_n) &= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot I_n[\textit{coin} \mapsto 0] + \frac{2}{3} \cdot I_n[\textit{win} \mapsto \textit{win} + \textit{step}, \textit{coin} \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{3}}_{=1-2/3} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + 1 - \frac{2}{3} + \frac{2}{3} + \frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + 1 + \frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} + 1 + \frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{8}{3} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i + \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^i \right) \\
&= I_{n+1} .
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we proved that I_n is a lower and upper ω -invariant of loop $P_{\textit{while}}$ w.r.t. continuation $\mathbf{0}$.

Using the closed form of the geometric series, i.e. $\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} q^i = \frac{1}{1-p}$ for all $q \in \mathbb{R}$ with $|q| < 1$ [9], we compute

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n &= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{8}}{\mathbf{3}} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\mathbf{2}}{\mathbf{3}} \right)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\mathbf{2}}{\mathbf{3}} \right)^i \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{8}}{\mathbf{3}} \cdot \mathbf{3} + \mathbf{3} \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \mathbf{11} .
\end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 4.4, we finally obtain

$$\text{ert}[P_{\textit{while}}](\mathbf{0}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n = \mathbf{1} + [\textit{coin} = 1] \cdot \mathbf{11} .$$

Consequently, loop $P_{\textit{while}}$ has an expected run-time of 12 on each initial state assigning 1 to variable \textit{coin} and costs 1 unit of time on all other initial states. ■

In general, it is hard to find upper and lower ω -invariants to determine the expected run-time of loops. The results presented in [6] underline this: Deciding whether a given probabilistic program P has finite expected run-time on a given input until termination is strictly harder than solving the halting problem for ordinary non-probabilistic programs. In the next section, we present a class of loops for which it is easier to determine their expected run-time.

Chapter 5

Independent and Identically Distributed Loops

This chapter formally defines the class of i.i.d. loops and demonstrates how to verify that a given loop is independent and identically distributed. Furthermore, we provide a theorem characterising the wp semantics of these loops.

Independent and identically distributed loops (i.i.d. loops, for short) are loops where the set of states reached at the end of the different loop iterations are independent and identically distributed. This is the case whenever there is no data flow across its iterations [13]. Consider the following loop L as a first example:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{while}(x = 1)\{ \\ &\quad x := \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle \\ &\} \end{aligned}$$

It is not hard to see that whenever variable x is assigned to a certain value, that value is never read in a subsequent iteration and hence the loop is independent and identically distributed. Formally, we characterise i.i.d. loops as follows:

Definition 5.1 (Independent and identically distributed loops). Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard. We call loop $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$ *independent and identically distributed* (or *i.i.d.*) if for all $f \in \mathbb{E}$ it holds that

$$\text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) = \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) \quad \blacksquare$$

The following example demonstrates how to verify that a given loop is independent and identically distributed.

Example 5.2. We want to verify that loop L from above is an i.i.d. loop. Let P denote the loop body, i.e. the probabilistic assignment $x := \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle$. We have to check whether

$$\text{wp}[P]([x = 1] \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) = \text{wp}[P]([x = 1]) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) \quad (5.1)$$

for all $f \in \mathbb{E}$. Therefore, let $f \in \mathbb{E}$ be an arbitrary expectation. We compute

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{wp}[P]([x = 1] \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]\left([x = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1]\right)\right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left([x = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1]\right)\right)[x \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left([x = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1]\right)\right)[x \mapsto 1] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left([0 = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1] \right) \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left([1 = 1] \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1] \right) \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{4} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1]
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{wp}[P]([x = 1]) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot [0 = 1] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot [1 = 1] \right) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot [0 = 1] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot [1 = 1] \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1] \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{4} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{4} \cdot f[x \mapsto 1].
\end{aligned}$$

Since Equation 5.I holds, we have verified that L is indeed an i.i.d. loop. \blacksquare

In order to characterise the wp semantics of i.i.d. loops, we adapt the results from Olmedo et. al. presented in [13], who determine the wp semantics of independent and identically distributed $\text{repeat} \dots \text{until}$ loops.

Proving the results of this chapter requires the following technical lemma. Furthermore, given $P \in \text{pProgs}$ and expectations $f, g \in \mathbb{E}$, we define $\text{wp}[P]_g^0(f) = \text{wp}[P](f)$ and $\text{wp}[P]_g^{n+1}(f) = \text{wp}[P](g \cdot \text{wp}[P]_g^n(f))$.

Lemma 5.3. *Let $P \in \text{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard such that $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$ is an i.i.d. loop. Then for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$ and all $f \in \mathbb{E}$, we have*

$$\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil)^i = \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^i(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)).$$

Proof. By induction on i .

Base cases. For $i = 0$, we have

$$\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil)^0 = \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) = \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^0(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)).$$

For $i = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil)^1 &= \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil) \\
&= \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)) && \text{(By Def. 5.1)} \\
&= \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^1(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)).
\end{aligned}$$

Inductive step. Assuming the lemma holds for some $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $i > 0$ as induction hypothesis (I.H., for short), we compute

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil)^{i+1} \\
&= \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil)^i \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil) \\
&= \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^i(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil) && \text{(By I.H.)} \\
&= \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^{i-1}(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f))) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil) \\
&= \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil \cdot \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^{i-1}(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)))) && \text{(By Def. 5.1)} \\
&= \text{wp}[P](\lceil \varphi \rceil \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^i(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f))) \\
&= \text{wp}[P]_{\lceil \varphi \rceil}^{i+1}(\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f))
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

In order to obtain a characterisation of the **wp** semantics of an i.i.d. loop, we analyse the behaviour of its finite approximations, which are defined as follows:

Definition 5.4 (*n*-unrolling of a loop [3, p. 45]). Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard. The *n*-unrolling of loop $\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ is given by the following clauses:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{while}_0(\varphi) \{P\} &\triangleq \mathbf{abort} \\ \mathbf{while}_{n+1}(\varphi) \{P\} &\triangleq \mathbf{if}(\varphi) \{P; \mathbf{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}\} \mathbf{else} \{\mathbf{skip}\} \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Speaking intuitively, $\mathbf{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}$ is the program that simulates loop $\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ but terminates after at most n iterations.

The following lemma characterises the **wp** semantics of the finite approximations of an i.i.d. loop.

Lemma 5.5 (*wp* semantics of finite approximations of i.i.d. loops). Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard such that $\mathbf{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ is an i.i.d. loop. Then for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ and $f \in \mathbb{E}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}](f) \\ = [\varphi] \cdot \left(\mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f . \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By induction on n .

Base cases. For $n = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{while}_1(\varphi) \{P\}](f) \\ &= \mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{if}(\varphi) \{P; \mathbf{while}_0(\varphi) \{P\}\} \mathbf{else} \{\mathbf{skip}\}](f) && \text{(By Def. 5.4)} \\ &= \mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{if}(\varphi) \{P; \mathbf{abort}\} \mathbf{else} \{\mathbf{skip}\}](f) \\ &= [\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P](\mathbf{0}) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\ &= [\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{0} + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f && \text{(pres. of } \mathbf{0}) \\ &= [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\ &= [\varphi] \cdot \left(\mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{-1} \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f . \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{while}_2(\varphi) \{P\}](f) \\ &= \mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{if}(\varphi) \{P; \mathbf{while}_1(\varphi) \{P\}\} \mathbf{else} \{f\}](f) \\ &= [\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P](\mathbf{wp}[\mathbf{while}_1(\varphi) \{P\}](f)) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\ &= [\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\ &= [\varphi] \cdot \left(\mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^0 \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f . \end{aligned}$$

Inductive step. Observe the following equation implied by Lemma 5.3 and Definition 5.1.:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\ &= \mathbf{wp}[P] \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-2} [\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \mathbf{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) && \text{(Linearity of wp)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{[\varphi]}^i (\text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f)) \right) && \text{(By Lem. 5.3)} \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{[\varphi]}^i (\text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f)) && \text{(By Def. 5.1)} \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i && \text{(By Lem. 5.3)} \\
&= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i && (\dagger)
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming the lemma holds for some $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ as induction hypothesis, we compute

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{wp}[\text{while}_{n+1}(\varphi)\{P\}](f) \\
&= \text{wp}[\text{if}(\varphi)\{P; \text{while}_n(\varphi)\{P\}\} \text{else}\{\text{skip}\}](f) && \text{(By Def. 5.4)} \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P; \text{while}_n(\varphi)\{P\}](f) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P](\text{wp}[\text{while}_n(\varphi)\{P\}](f)) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} (\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f && \text{(By I.H.)} \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} (\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f && \text{(Linearity of wp)} \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} (\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f && \text{(By } (\dagger)) \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f \\
&= [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f .
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Having that characterisation at hand, we obtain the wp semantics of an entire i.i.d. loop by using the fact that the limit of the finite approximations describes the behaviour of the entire loop.

Theorem 5.6 (wp semantics of i.i.d. loops). *Let $P \in \text{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard such that $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$ is an i.i.d. loop. Then the following two statements hold for all $f \in \mathbb{E}$:*

1. For all $\sigma \in \Sigma$ with $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) < 1$, we have

$$\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) = [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \frac{\text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f)(\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) .$$

2. For all $\sigma \in \Sigma$ with $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$, we have

$$\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) = [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) .$$

Proof. The proof relies on a result presented in [3, p. 47]: For all $P \in \text{pProgs}$ and every guard φ , we have

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{wp}[\text{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}](f) = \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f) ,$$

implying

$$\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{wp}[\text{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) = \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) \quad (5.II)$$

for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$.

Proof of 1. Assume $\text{wp}[P](\llbracket\varphi\rrbracket)(\sigma) < 1$. Using the closed form of the geometric series, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) \\ &= \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{wp}[\text{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) && \text{(By Equation 5.II)} \\ &= \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P](\llbracket\neg\varphi\rrbracket \cdot f)(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \text{wp}[P](\llbracket\varphi\rrbracket)(\sigma)^i \right) + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \\ & && \text{(By Lemma 5.5)} \\ &= [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P](\llbracket\neg\varphi\rrbracket \cdot f)(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \text{wp}[P](\llbracket\varphi\rrbracket)(\sigma)^i \right) + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \\ &= [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \frac{\text{wp}[P](\llbracket\neg\varphi\rrbracket \cdot f)(\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P](\llbracket\varphi\rrbracket)(\sigma)} + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) . && \text{(Geometric series)} \end{aligned}$$

Proof of 2. Assume $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) \\ &= \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{wp}[\text{while}_n(\varphi) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) && \text{(By Equation 5.II)} \\ &= \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \underbrace{[\varphi](\sigma)}_{=0} \cdot \left(\text{wp}[P](\llbracket\neg\varphi\rrbracket \cdot f)(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-2} \text{wp}[P](\llbracket\varphi\rrbracket)(\sigma)^i \right) + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \\ & && \text{(By Lemma 5.5)} \\ &= \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) = [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) . \end{aligned}$$

□

We want to demonstrate how to apply Theorem 5.6.

Example 5.7. Consider the following loop L :

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{while}(x = 1)\{ \\ & \quad x := \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle \\ & \} \end{aligned}$$

In Example 5.2, we have verified that L is indeed an i.i.d. loop. Hence, we can apply Theorem 5.6 to obtain the wp semantics of L . Let P denote the loop body and $f \in \mathbb{E}$ be an arbitrary expectation. We need to compute $\text{wp}[P]([x \neq 1] \cdot f)$ and $\text{wp}[P]([x = 1])$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P]([x \neq 1] \cdot f) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot ([x \neq 1] \cdot f)[x \mapsto 0] + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \cdot ([x \neq 1] \cdot f)[x \mapsto 1]}_{=0} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\text{wp}[P]([x = 1]) = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \cdot ([x = 1])[x \mapsto 0]}_{=0} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot ([x = 1])[x \mapsto 1] = \frac{1}{2}.$$

As $\text{wp}[P]([x = 1])(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2} < 1$ for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$, Theorem 5.6 yields

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[\text{while}(x = 1) \{P\}](f)(\sigma) &= [x = 1](\sigma) \cdot \frac{\text{wp}[P]([x \neq 1] \cdot f)}{\text{wp}[P]([x = 1])} + [x \neq 1](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \\ &= [x = 1](\sigma) \cdot \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot f[x \mapsto 0](\sigma)}{\frac{1}{2}} + [x \neq 1](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \\ &= [x = 1](\sigma) \cdot f[x \mapsto 0](\sigma) + [x \neq 1](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \end{aligned}$$

for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$, which implies

$$\text{wp}[\text{while}(x = 1) \{P\}](f) = [x = 1] \cdot f[x \mapsto 0] + [x \neq 1] \cdot f. \quad \blacksquare$$

Theorem 5.6 is used in the next chapter to establish the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops.

Chapter 6

Expected Run-Times of i.i.d. Loops

In this chapter, we present a proof rule to compute expected run-times of i.i.d. loops. We first present the proof rule, discuss its premises, and provide an example demonstrating how to apply it. Afterwards, we provide the correctness proof together with the technical results the proof relies on.

6.1 A Proof Rule for Expected Run-Times of i.i.d. Loops

The proof rule we propose in this section can reduce the effort of computing expected run-time of i.i.d. loops to syntactic reasoning. If a given loop fulfils the premises of the proof rule, it suffices to reason about the wp semantics and the expected run-time of the loop body in order to obtain the loop's expected run-time.

Theorem 6.1 (Proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops). *Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$, φ be a guard and $f \in \mathbb{T}$ be a continuation. Furthermore, assume the following conditions hold:*

1. *Loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ is independent and identically distributed.*
2. $\text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$.
3. $\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}](f) \\ &= \mathbf{1} + \frac{[\varphi]}{\mathbf{1} - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)) + \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f, \end{aligned} \quad (6.I)$$

where $\frac{0}{0} \triangleq 0$ and $\frac{1}{0} \triangleq \infty$.

Note that $1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)$ denotes the probability of the guard evaluating to false (resp. 0) after one iteration on initial state σ . If $1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) = 0$, the loop does not terminate which results in an infinite expected run-time. On the other hand, if $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$, the loop is not executed, which yields the loop to have an expected run-time of 1 due to the first guard evaluation. Therefore, Equation 6.I is a shorthand for

$$\text{ert} [\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}] (f) (\sigma) = \begin{cases} 1 + \frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])} \cdot (1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)(\sigma)) + \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil(\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma), & \text{if } \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) < 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } [\varphi](\sigma) = 0 \\ \infty, & \text{if } [\varphi](\sigma) = 1 \\ & \wedge \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) = 1 \end{cases} .$$

In order to apply the proof rule to a given i.i.d. loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ and given continuation $f \in \mathbb{T}$, we need to perform several steps. We first need to verify that the given loop is indeed independent and identically distributed (condition 1). Furthermore, we need to show $\text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$ (condition 2). As $\text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1})(\sigma)$ denotes the probability that program P terminates on initial state σ [14], the second condition expresses that the loop body terminates with probability 1 on every initial state. In this case, we also say that program P *terminates almost-surely* on each initial state. To get a deeper understanding of the third condition, observe the following theorem establishing a connection between the two transformers wp and ert .

Theorem 6.2 (Connection between ert and wp [14]). *For every program $P \in \text{pProgs}$ and run-time $f \in \mathbb{T}$, we have*

$$\text{ert}[P](f) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](f) .$$

By applying Theorem 6.2, we obtain that $\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$ is equivalent to $\text{ert}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \mathbf{2} \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$ due to the following reasoning:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) &= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \\ \iff \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) &= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \\ \iff \text{ert}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) &= \mathbf{2} \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \quad (\text{By Theorem 6.2}) \end{aligned}$$

Speaking intuitively, this condition expresses that the loop body P has the same expected run-time on each iteration.

Once we have verified that a given loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ fulfils conditions 1 to 3, we obtain the expected run-time of that loop w.r.t. continuation $f \in \mathbb{T}$ by computing

- $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])$,
- $\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$,
- $\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)$,

and by plugging the results into the following equation:

$$\text{ert} [\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}] (f) = \mathbf{1} + \frac{[\varphi]}{\mathbf{1} - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)) + \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f$$

If the loop body P is loop-free, then the different components can be computed mostly by means of syntactic reasoning. We want to apply the proof rule to an example.

Example 6.3. Consider the following loop L adapted from [13]:

```

1  while( $i > 6$ ){
2     $a_0, a_1, a_2 \approx \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle 1 \rangle$ ;
3     $i := 4a_2 + 2a_1 + a_0 + 1$ 
4  }
```

The loop simulates a six-sided die, i.e. a uniform distribution over $\{1, \dots, 6\}$, by means of three fair coin tosses. We want to determine the average number of guard evaluations and assignments necessary to simulate that distribution. Therefore, we apply Theorem 6.1 to compute $\text{ert}[\text{while}(i > 6) \{P_{\text{body}}\}](\mathbf{0})$ where P_{body} denotes the body of loop L . For $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, let P_j denote the program in line j and let $f \in \mathbb{E}$ be an arbitrary expectation. In order to verify that loop L is indeed i.i.d., we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f) &= \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 1, a_0, a_1, a_2 \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 2, a_0 \mapsto 1, a_1, a_2 \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 3, a_1 \mapsto 1, a_0, a_2 \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 4, a_0, a_1 \mapsto 1, a_2 \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 5, a_2 \mapsto 1, a_0, a_1 \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 6, a_0, a_2 \mapsto 1, a_1 \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 7, a_1, a_2 \mapsto 1, a_0 \mapsto 0] + \frac{1}{8} \cdot f[i \mapsto 8, a_0, a_1, a_2 \mapsto 1] . \end{aligned}$$

Observe that variables a_0, a_1, a_2 , and i do not occur in $\text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f)$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([i > 6] \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f)) &= \text{wp}[P_2; P_3]([i > 6] \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_2](\text{wp}[P_3]([i > 6] \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f))) \quad (i \text{ does not occur in } \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_2](\text{wp}[P_3]([i > 6])) \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f) \\ &\quad (a_0, a_1, a_2 \text{ do not occur in } \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([i > 6]) \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](f) . \end{aligned}$$

Hence, loop L is indeed independent and identically distributed.

The second condition, i.e. $\text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$, is valid because every loop-free program terminates almost-surely on each initial state. Furthermore, as $\text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{4}$ and by linearity of wp , we get

$$\text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](\text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{0})) = \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{4}) = \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](4 \cdot \mathbf{1}) = 4 \cdot \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{1}) = 4 \cdot \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{4} .$$

This verifies the third condition. Having verified all three conditions of Theorem 6.1, we can proceed by computing

- $\text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([i > 6]) = \frac{1}{4}$,
- $\text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{4}$, and
- $\text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([i \leq 6] \cdot \mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{0}$.

Thus, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ert}[\text{while}(i > 6) \{P_{\text{body}}\}](\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + \frac{[i > 6]}{\mathbf{1} - \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([i > 6])} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([i \leq 6] \cdot \mathbf{0})) + [i \leq 6] \cdot \mathbf{0} \\ &= \mathbf{1} + \frac{\mathbf{4} \cdot [i > 6]}{\mathbf{3}} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{4}) = \mathbf{1} + [i > 6] \cdot \frac{\mathbf{20}}{\mathbf{3}} . \end{aligned}$$

Hence, if $i > 6$ when entering the loop, its expected run-time is $1 + \frac{20}{3} \approx 7.67$. ■

6.2 Correctness Proof

In order to prove Theorem 6.1, we proceed as follows: Assume we are given an arbitrary i.i.d. loop $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$ and a continuation $f \in \mathbb{T}$. Theorem 6.2 allows to split the computation of $\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)$ into computing $\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})$ and $\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)$. The latter is already given by the characterisation of the wp semantics of i.i.d. loops developed in Chapter 5, i.e. by Theorem 5.6. To obtain $\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})$, we provide a parametrized run-time which is both a lower and upper ω -invariant of loop $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$ w.r.t. to continuation $\mathbf{0}$ and apply Theorem 4.4. The following equation summarizes the procedure:

$$\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f) \stackrel{\text{By Thm. 6.2}}{=} \underbrace{\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})}_{\text{By } \omega\text{-invariant}} + \underbrace{\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)}_{\text{By Thm. 5.6}}$$

Proving the ω -invariant correct requires the following two technical lemmata.

Lemma 6.4. *Let $P \in \text{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard such that $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$ is an i.i.d. loop. Furthermore, assume*

$$\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) . \quad (6.II)$$

Then

$$\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket)^i = \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^i(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))$$

for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. By induction on i .

Base cases. For $i = 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket)^0 &= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \\ &= \text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) && \text{(By Equation 6.II)} \\ &= \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^0(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) . \end{aligned}$$

For $i = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket)^1 &= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket) \\ &= \text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket) && \text{(By Equation 6.II)} \\ &= \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket \cdot \text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))) && \text{(By Def. 5.1)} \\ &= \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^1(\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^1(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) . && \text{(By Equation 6.II)} \end{aligned}$$

Inductive step. Assume the lemma holds for some $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $i > 0$ as induction hypothesis (I.H., for short). We compute

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket)^{i+1} &= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket)^i \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^i(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket) && \text{(By I.H.)} \\ &= \text{wp}[P]\left(\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^{i-1}(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))\right) \cdot \text{wp}[P](\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]\left(\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket \cdot \text{wp}[P]\left(\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket \cdot \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^{i-1}(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))\right)\right) \\ & && \text{(By Def. 5.1)} \\ &= \text{wp}[P]_{\llbracket \varphi \rrbracket}^{i+1}(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) . \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 6.5. *Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$ and φ be a guard such that $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ is an i.i.d. loop. By applying Definition 5.1 multiple times, we have*

$$\text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i = \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i)$$

for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. By induction on i .

Base cases. For $i = 0$, we have

$$\text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^0 = \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \mathbf{1} = \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) .$$

For $i = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^1 &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])) . \end{aligned} \quad (\text{By Def. 5.1})$$

Inductive step. Assume the lemma holds for some $i \in \mathbb{N}$ with $i > 0$ as induction hypothesis. We compute

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^{i+1} &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \quad (\text{By I.H.}) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i)) \quad (\text{By Def. 5.1}) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) \quad (\text{By I.H.}) \\ &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^{i+1}) . \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Equipped with the presented technical results, we are now in a position to propose the ω -invariant for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops.

Lemma 6.6. *Let $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}$. Furthermore, let φ be a guard such that $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ is an i.i.d. loop. If*

$$\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \quad (6.\text{III})$$

and

$$\text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1} , \quad (6.\text{IV})$$

then the following is both an upper and lower ω -invariant of loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ with respect to continuation $\mathbf{0}$:

$$I_n = \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right)$$

Proof. Let $F_{\mathbf{0}}$ denote the characteristic functional of loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ with respect to continuation $\mathbf{0}$. In order to verify I_n as both an upper and lower ω -invariant we first show $F_{\mathbf{0}}(\mathbf{0}) = I_0$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\mathbf{0}}(\mathbf{0}) &= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \\ &= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^0 \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i + \sum_{i=0}^{0-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\ &= I_0 . \end{aligned}$$

We also verify $F_0(I_0) = I_1$ to avoid expressions like $\sum_{i=0}^{-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i$ in base cases. We compute

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0(I_0) &= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](I_0) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))) && \text{(By Theorem 6.2)} \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) + \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))) && \text{(Linearity of wp)} \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \mathbf{1} + \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}))) && \text{(By Equation 6.IV)} \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \mathbf{1} + \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) && \text{(By Lemma 6.4 with } i = 1\text{)} \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^1 \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i + \sum_{i=0}^0 \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\
&= I_1 .
\end{aligned}$$

Before we prove the remaining proof obligation, observe the following equations. Lemma 6.4 yields

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\
&= \text{wp}[P] \left(\sum_{i=0}^n [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) && \text{(Linearity of wp)} \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i && \text{(By Lemma 6.4)} \\
&= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \\
&= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i . && \text{(6.V)}
\end{aligned}$$

Moreover, Lemma 6.5 implies

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i) . && \text{(Linearity of wp)} \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i && \text{(By Lemma 6.5)} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])^i . && \text{(6.VI)}
\end{aligned}$$

We are now in a position to show $F_0(I_n) = I_{n+1}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
F_0(I_n) &= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot (\text{ert}[P](I_n)) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](I_n)) && \text{(By Theorem 6.2)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P] \left(\mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right) \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P] \left(\mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) + [\varphi] \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) + \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right) \quad (\text{Linearity of wp}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \mathbf{1} + \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right) \quad (\text{By Equation 6.IV}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \text{wp}[P] \left([\varphi] \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \right) \quad (\text{By Equation 6.V}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + \mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{i=1}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \quad (\text{By Equation 6.VI}) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + [\varphi] \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) + \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]^i) \right) \\
&= I_{n+1} .
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

The presented ω -invariant finally allows to prove Theorem 6.1.

Proof of Theorem 6.1. We prove the theorem point-wise, i.e. for every state $\sigma \in \Sigma$, we show

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \\
&= \mathbf{1} + \frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} \cdot (1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[P]([\neg\varphi] \cdot f)(\sigma)) + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) .
\end{aligned}$$

First recall

$$\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f) = \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f) ,$$

implying

$$\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) = \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \quad (6.VII)$$

for all $\sigma \in \Sigma$. We distinguish between two cases, namely $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) < 1$ and $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) = 1$.

First case. Assume $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) < 1$.

Applying Theorem 4.4, Lemma 6.6 and the closed form of the geometric series yields

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)^i \right) \right) \\
&= 1 + [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)^i \right) \\
&\hspace{15em} \text{(Both sums converge absolute)} \\
&= 1 + [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \left(\frac{\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} + \frac{1}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} \right) \quad \text{(Geom. Series)} \\
&= 1 + \frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + 1) . \quad (6.VIII)
\end{aligned}$$

Moreover, as $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) < 1$, the first statement of Theorem 5.6 yields

$$\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) = [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \frac{\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)(\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} + \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil(\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) . \quad (6.IX)$$

Using Equation 6.VII and putting Equation 6.VIII and Equation 6.IX together, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \\
&= \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \quad \text{(By Equation 6.VII)} \\
&= 1 + \frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} (\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}) + 1) \\
&\quad + [\varphi](\sigma) \cdot \frac{\text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)(\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} + \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil(\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) \\
&\hspace{15em} \text{(By Equation 6.VIII and Equation 6.IX)} \\
&= 1 + \frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)} \cdot (1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[P](\lceil \neg \varphi \rceil \cdot f)(\sigma)) + \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil(\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) .
\end{aligned}$$

Second case. Assume $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma) = 1$.

We distinguish between two cases again, namely $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$ and $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$. First assume $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$. Then from Theorem 4.4 and Lemma 6.6 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \underbrace{[\varphi](\sigma)}_{=0} \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)^i + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \text{wp}[P]([\varphi])(\sigma)^i \right) \right) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} 1 = 1 . \quad (6.X)
\end{aligned}$$

This agrees with the intuition: As the loop guard is not satisfied, the loop is not executed and the expected run-time of the loop equals 1 because of the guard evaluation. Furthermore, as $[\varphi](\sigma) = 0$, the second statement of Theorem 5.6 yields

$$\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) = \lceil \neg \varphi \rceil(\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) . \quad (6.XI)$$

Using Equation 6.VII and putting Equation 6.X and Equation 6.XI together, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \\
&= \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \quad \text{(By Equation 6.VII)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 1 + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) && \text{(By Equation 6.X and Equation 6.XI)} \\
&= 1 + \underbrace{\frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi](\sigma))}}_{=\frac{0}{0}=:0} \cdot (1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[P](\lceil\neg\varphi\rceil \cdot f)(\sigma)) + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) .
\end{aligned}$$

To prove the remaining case, assume $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$. Then from Theorem 4.4 and Lemma 6.6 it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} 1 + \underbrace{[\varphi](\sigma)}_{=1} \cdot \left(\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n \underbrace{\text{wp}[P]([\varphi](\sigma))^i}_{=1} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \underbrace{\text{wp}[P]([\varphi](\sigma))^i}_{=1} \right) \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} 1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n 1 + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} 1 \\
&= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} 1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) \cdot (n+1) + n \\
&= \infty . && \text{(6.XII)}
\end{aligned}$$

Using Equation 6.VII and Equation 6.XII, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) \\
&= \text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma) && \text{(By Equation 6.VII)} \\
&= \infty + \underbrace{\text{wp}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}](f)(\sigma)}_{\geq 0} = \infty && \text{(By Equation 6.XII)} \\
&= 1 + \underbrace{\frac{[\varphi](\sigma)}{1 - \text{wp}[P]([\varphi](\sigma))}}_{=\frac{1}{0}=: \infty} \cdot \underbrace{(1 + \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})(\sigma) + \text{wp}[P](\lceil\neg\varphi\rceil \cdot f)(\sigma))}_{\geq 1} + [\neg\varphi](\sigma) \cdot f(\sigma) .
\end{aligned}$$

This also agrees with the intuition: As $[\varphi](\sigma) = 1$, the loop is executed and as $\text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) = 1$, the loop does not terminate, resulting in an infinite expected run-time. \square

Chapter 7

Application: Expected Simulation Time of Bayesian Networks

In this chapter, we introduce Bayesian Networks and formally define how to simulate them by means of probabilistic programs. Furthermore, we show that the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops can be applied to automatically compute the expected simulation time of Bayesian Network, i.e. the average number of guard evaluations and assignments necessary to simulate the network.

Probabilistic graphical models use graphs to denote conditional dependencies between random variables. Their application areas include information extraction, speech recognition, coding theory, biology and reliability analysis [2]. A *Bayesian Network* [8] is such a model. It provides a compact representation of the joint distribution of some finite set of random variables $\mathcal{X} = \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$.

7.1 Bayesian Networks and Probabilistic Programs

According to [2]: A *Bayesian Network* is a directed acyclic graph $G = (V, E)$. Every node $v \in V$ is associated with a random variable X_v and every edge $(u, v) \in E$ represents a direct dependence from the random variable X_u to the random variable X_v . We assume that the random variables are discrete and take values from a finite domain denoted by $\text{Val}(v)$ for $v \in V$. Let $\text{Deps}(v) = \{u \mid (u, v) \in E\}$ denote the direct dependencies of node $v \in V$. Each node $v \in V$ is associated with a *conditional probability distribution* CPD_v , which denotes the probability distribution of X_v conditioned over values of the random variables associated with the direct dependencies $\text{Deps}(v)$. If $\text{Deps}(v) = \{v_1, \dots, v_l\}$, then CPD_v is given as a function

$$\text{CPD}_v : \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_l) \times \text{Val}(v) \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

satisfying $\sum_{a \in \text{Val}(v)} \text{CPD}_v(a_1, \dots, a_l, a) = 1$ for all $(a_1, \dots, a_l) \in \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_l)$. Hence, the conditional probability distribution at each node can be represented by a table as shown in Figure 7.1.

The Bayesian Network shown in Figure 7.1 models how the grade a student obtains is affected by the difficulty of the course and by the student's intelligence and how the grade affects her mood. We abbreviate the corresponding random variables with their first letters D, I, G and M . The joint distribution of these random variables is determined by the *chain rule for Bayesian Networks* [8, p.62], i.e.

$$P(D, I, G, M) = P(D) \cdot P(I) \cdot P(G \mid I, D) \cdot P(M \mid G) .$$

Figure 7.1: Bayesian Network example adapted from [8].

Hence, we compute the joint distribution by starting at the nodes without dependencies and proceed in topological order. For instance, the probability that the course is easy ($D = 0$), that a student is intelligent ($I = 0$), that she obtains a bad grade ($G = 1$) and that she will be in a good mood ($M = 0$) is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P(D = 0, I = 0, G = 1, M = 0) \\
 &= P(D = 0) \cdot P(I = 0) \cdot P(G = 1 \mid D = 0, I = 0) \cdot P(M = 0 \mid G = 1) \\
 &= 0.6 \cdot 0.7 \cdot 0.05 \cdot 0.3 = 0.0063 .
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that probabilities like $P(D = 0)$ or $P(G = 1 \mid D = 0, I = 0)$ are given by the tables shown in Figure 7.1, i.e. by the CPD associated with each node.

Probabilistic programs can be used to simulate Bayesian Networks. In order to simulate a Bayesian Network by means of a probabilistic program, we introduce a program variable for each random variable, i.e. each node, in the Bayesian Network and use probabilistic assignments and conditionals to encode the conditional probability distribution associated with each node. The program shown in Example 1 of Figure 7.2 encodes the Bayesian Network from above: The joint distribution of the program variables agrees with the joint distribution of the random variables given by the Bayesian Network. For instance, the probability of the program terminating in a state σ with $\sigma(g) = 1$ and $\sigma(m) = 0$ agrees with the probability that the student obtains a bad grade and that she is in a good, i.e.

$$\text{wp}[E_1]([g = 1 \wedge m = 0]) = P(G = 1, M = 0) .$$

Suppose we are interested in the probability of the student being in a good mood ($M = 0$) given that he obtains a good grade ($G = 0$), i.e. we are interested in $P(M = 0 \mid G = 0)$. Thus, we need to condition the value of random variable G to 0. Example 2 of Figure 7.2 demonstrates how to encode *conditioning*. Gretz et. al. [3] provide evidence that we can condition the value of program variable g to 0 by embedding the part of the program simulating the conditional probability distribution of random variable G in a loop (line 4). The loop ensures that as long as program variable g is not assigned to value 0, a new value is sampled. Thus, variable g will be assigned to 0 when the loop terminates. In order to ensure that the loop performs at least one iteration, we assign g to value $\diamond \notin \text{Val}(G)$ (line 3). Hence, the probability of the program terminating in a state σ with $\sigma(m) = 0$ agrees with $P(M = 0 \mid G = 0)$ given by the Bayesian Network, i.e.

$$\text{wp}[E_2]([m = 0]) = P(M = 0 \mid G = 0) .$$

Whenever we embed the simulation of a conditional probability distribution in a loop as

<pre> 1 d := 0.6 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.4 · ⟨1⟩; 2 i := 0.7 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.3 · ⟨1⟩; 3 if(d = 0 ∧ i = 0){ 4 g := 0.95 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.05 · ⟨1⟩; 5 if(d = 1 ∧ i = 1){ 6 g := 0.05 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.95 · ⟨1⟩; 7 if(d = 0 ∧ i = 1){ 8 g := 0.5 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.5 · ⟨1⟩; 9 if(d = 1 ∧ i = 0){ 10 g := 0.6 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.4 · ⟨1⟩; 11 if(g = 0){ 12 m := 0.9 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.1 · ⟨1⟩; 13 if(g = 1){ 14 m := 0.3 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.7 · ⟨1⟩ </pre>	<pre> 1 d := 0.6 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.4 · ⟨1⟩; 2 i := 0.7 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.3 · ⟨1⟩; 3 g := ∅; // ∅ ∉ Val(G) 4 while(g ≠ 0){ 5 if(d = 0 ∧ i = 0){ 6 g := 0.95 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.05 · ⟨1⟩; 7 if(d = 1 ∧ i = 1){ 8 g := 0.05 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.95 · ⟨1⟩; 9 if(d = 0 ∧ i = 1){ 10 g := 0.5 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.5 · ⟨1⟩; 11 if(d = 1 ∧ i = 0){ 12 g := 0.6 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.4 · ⟨1⟩ 13 }; 14 if(g = 0){ 15 m := 0.9 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.1 · ⟨1⟩; 16 if(g = 1){ 17 m := 0.3 · ⟨0⟩ + 0.7 · ⟨1⟩ </pre>
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Example 1 (Program E_1)Example 2 (Program E_2)

Figure 7.2: Encoding Bayesian Networks as probabilistic programs.

demonstrated in Example 2 of Figure 7.2 we obtain an independent and identically distributed loop. Moreover, those loops fulfil all three premises of the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops presented in Chapter 6. As the loop body of those loops is loop-free, we can apply the proof rule to compute the expected run-time of those loops automatically. In order to proof this, we define a fragment $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ of the presented probabilistic programming language pProgs fulfilling two requirements:

1. It has to be powerful enough to encode Bayesian Networks and conditioning.
2. The proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops can be applied to every loop of that fragment, i.e. every loop fulfils all three conditions of Theorem 6.1.

The idea is to define a fragment such that it is impossible to write loops which have data flow across their iterations. We achieve this by restricting the grammar for loop bodies. Every loop body may only be of the form

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{if}(\varphi_1)\{ \\
 \quad x_1 := p_{1,1} \cdot \langle a_{1,1} \rangle + \dots + p_{1,m_1} \cdot \langle a_{1,m_1} \rangle \\
 \}; \\
 \vdots \\
 \text{if}(\varphi_n)\{ \\
 \quad x_n := p_{n,1} \cdot \langle a_{n,1} \rangle + \dots + p_{n,m_n} \cdot \langle a_{n,m_n} \rangle \\
 \} ,
 \end{array}$$

where each $a_{i,j}$ is a *value* and no guard φ_i contains one of the variables x_1, \dots, x_n . Hence, whenever a variable x_i is set in an iteration, its value is never read in a subsequent iteration. We formalize this idea by means of a context-free grammar.

Definition 7.1 (Loop bodies in $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$). The set of loop bodies $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$ is given by the grammar

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}} ::= & \quad \text{if}(\varphi) \{x \approx p_1 \cdot \langle a_1 \rangle + \dots + p_n \cdot \langle a_n \rangle\} && \text{conditional probabilistic assignment} \\ & \mid \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}; \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}} && \text{sequential composition} \end{aligned}$$

where

- $a_1, \dots, a_n \in \mathbf{Val}$, $p_1, \dots, p_n \in [0, 1]$ with $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$.
- $\mathbf{Var}_{\text{Assign}}, \mathbf{Var}_{\text{Guard}} \subset \mathbf{Var}$ with $\mathbf{Var}_{\text{Assign}} \cap \mathbf{Var}_{\text{Guard}} = \emptyset$.
- $x \in \mathbf{Var}_{\text{Assign}}$.
- φ contains variables in $\mathbf{Var}_{\text{Guard}}$ only. ■

Remark. Even though the grammar does not allow for probabilistic assignments $x \approx \mu$ without surrounding conditionals they can be simulated by the program $\text{if}(\text{true})\{x \approx \mu\}$. The above restricted form is only chosen to simplify formal proofs. ■

The definition of $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ only differs in the way it allows to build loops.

Definition 7.2 (Fragment $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$). The restricted set of probabilistic programs $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ is given by the grammar

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}} ::= & \quad \text{empty} && \text{empty program} \\ & \mid \text{skip} && \text{effectless operation} \\ & \mid \text{halt} && \text{error} \\ & \mid x \approx \mu && \text{probabilistic assignment} \\ & \mid \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}}; \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}} && \text{sequential composition} \\ & \mid \text{if}(\varphi) \{ \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}} \} \text{ else } \{ \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}} \} && \text{conditional} \\ & \mid \text{while}(\varphi) \{ \mathcal{C}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}} \} && \text{restricted while loop} \end{aligned}$$

where $x \in \mathbf{Var}$, $\mu \in \mathbf{DExp}$ and φ is a guard. ■

The next section provides a proof that every loop in $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ fulfils all three premises of the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops. In the following, we formally define how to encode a Bayesian Network by means of a program $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$.

Suppose we are given a Bayesian Network $G = (V, E)$ with corresponding conditional probability distributions CPD_v for all $v \in V$. We denote the program variable associated with node v by x_v . Furthermore, assume we are given a set of conditions $\text{Cond}(x_v)$ on x_v for each $v \in V$, i.e. a set of Boolean expressions over x_v . We first define how to encode the conditional probability distribution and corresponding conditions associated with each node. Afterwards, we show how to compose these encodings such that the resulting program simulates the Bayesian Network.

Encoding conditional probability distributions and conditions. Let $v \in V$ and $\text{Deps}(v) = \{v_1, \dots, v_n\}$. Recall that CPD_v is given as a function

$$\text{CPD}_v: \mathbf{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \mathbf{Val}(v_n) \times \mathbf{Val}(v) \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

satisfying $\sum_{a \in \text{Val}(v)} \text{CPD}_v(a_1, \dots, a_n, a) = 1$ for all $(a_1, \dots, a_n) \in \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_n)$. In order to encode the different rows of CPD_v , we define a function

$$\llbracket v \rrbracket : \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_n) \rightarrow \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}.$$

If $n = 0$, then

$$\llbracket v \rrbracket(()) \triangleq x_v := \sum_{a \in \text{Val}(v)} \text{CPD}_v(a) \cdot \langle a \rangle,$$

where $()$ denotes the empty tuple. If $n \neq 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \llbracket v \rrbracket(a_1, \dots, a_n) &\triangleq \text{if}(x_{v_1} = a_1 \wedge \dots \wedge x_{v_n} = a_n) \{ \\ &x_v := \sum_{a \in \text{Val}(v)} \text{CPD}_v(a_1, \dots, a_n, a) \cdot \langle a \rangle \}. \end{aligned}$$

For $\bar{a}_1, \bar{a}_2 \in \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_n)$, we define

$$\llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}_1) \oplus \llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}_2) \triangleq \llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}_1); \llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}_2)$$

as the sequential composition of programs $\llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}_1)$ and $\llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}_2)$. We denote the program encoding node v by P_v . If $\text{Cond}(x_v) = \emptyset$, then

$$P_v \triangleq \bigoplus_{\bar{a} \in \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_n)} \llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}).$$

If $\text{Cond}(x_v) = \{c_1, \dots, c_m\}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} P_v &\triangleq x_v := \diamond; \\ &\text{while}(\neg c_1 \vee \dots \vee \neg c_m) \{ \\ &\quad \bigoplus_{\bar{a} \in \text{Val}(v_1) \times \dots \times \text{Val}(v_n)} \llbracket v \rrbracket(\bar{a}) \\ &\}. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that $P_v \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ for all $v \in V$.

Encoding the Bayesian Network. We now show how to compose the different encodings of the nodes and associated conditional probability distributions and assignments such that the resulting program simulates the Bayesian Network. Given a graph $G = (V, E)$, we let $L(G)$ denote the set of leaves, i.e. the set of nodes with no outgoing edges. Furthermore, given a subset of nodes $S \subseteq V$, we define

$$G \setminus S := (V \setminus S, E \setminus (\{(u, v) \mid u \in V, v \in S\} \cup \{(u, v) \mid u \in S, v \in V\}))$$

as the graph obtained from G when deleting all nodes from S . Since G is acyclic, we can define program BP_G encoding the Bayesian Network recursively as follows: If $G = (\emptyset, \emptyset)$, then $\text{BP}_G = \text{empty}$. Otherwise, i.e. if $L(G) = \{l_1, \dots, l_n\}$ for some $n > 0$, then

$$\text{BP}_G = \text{BP}_{G \setminus L(G)}; P',$$

where $P' = P_{l_1}; \dots; P_{l_n}$ and where P_{l_i} is the encoding of node l_i for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Hence, the *expected simulation time* of a Bayesian Network G is given by $\text{ert}[\text{BP}_G](\mathbf{0})$. Observe that $\text{BP}_G \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$.

7.2 Expected Simulation Time of Bayesian Networks

The goal of this section is to prove that the expected simulation time $\text{ert}[\text{BP}_G](\mathbf{0})$ of a given Bayesian Network G is a *computable* function. Speaking intuitively, the expected simulation time of Bayesian Network corresponds to the average number of guard evaluations and

assignments necessary until all conditions are satisfied and every value is sampled. Towards this end, we show that every loop in $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ fulfils all three premises of the proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops presented in Chapter 6.

Every $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$ is of the form $P = P_1; \dots; P_n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$, where each P_i is a conditional probabilistic assignment

$$\text{if}(\varphi_i) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_i : \approx p_{i,1} \cdot \langle a_{i,1} \rangle + \dots + p_{i,m_i} \cdot \langle a_{i,m_i} \rangle \\ \end{array} \right\}$$

as defined above. Moreover, for every conditional probabilistic assignment P_i and every expectation $f \in \mathbb{E}$, we have

$$\mathbf{wp}[P_i](f) = [\varphi_i] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot f[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \right) + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot f. \quad (7.I)$$

The following theorem states that every loop in $\mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ fulfils all three conditions of Theorem 6.1, i.e. the proof rule can be applied to compute the expected run-time of every loop in that fragment.

Theorem 7.3. *Let φ be an arbitrary guard and $P \in \mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$. We have*

1. Loop $\text{while}(\varphi) \{P\}$ is independent and identically distributed.
2. $\mathbf{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$.
3. $\mathbf{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$.

Each statement is proven separately.

Proof of 1. We have to show

$$\mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P](f)) = \mathbf{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P](f)$$

for every guard φ , every $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$ and all expectations $f \in \mathbb{E}$. To do so, we need some notation and technical lemmata. We first show that for all $f \in \mathbb{E}$ and $1 \leq i \leq n$, pre-expectation $\mathbf{wp}[P](f)$ can be represented as a sum of two expectations such that variable x_i does not occur in one of these expectations (Lemma 7.4). Afterwards, this result is used to prove $\mathbf{wp}[P_i](u \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P](f)) = \mathbf{wp}[P_i](u) \cdot \mathbf{wp}[P](f)$ for all $f, u \in \mathbb{E}$ and $1 \leq i \leq n$ (Lemma 7.5). This finally implies the validity of the i.i.d. property (Lemma 7.6).

For $h \in \mathbb{E}$, let $\mathbf{Var}(h) \subseteq \mathbf{Var}$ denote the set of all variables occurring in h . Moreover, for $x \in \mathbf{Var}$, we define $\mathbb{E}_{\setminus x} \triangleq \{f \in \mathbb{E} \mid x \notin \mathbf{Var}(f)\}$ as the set of expectations in which x does not occur.

Lemma 7.4. *For all $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \mathbf{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$, all expectations $f \in \mathbb{E}$ and every $1 \leq i \leq n$, there exist expectations $g \in \mathbb{E}$ and $h \in \mathbb{E}_{\setminus x_i}$ such that*

$$\mathbf{wp}[P](f) = [\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g. \quad (7.II)$$

Proof. By induction on n .

Base case. For a conditional probabilistic assignment P_1 , we have

$$\mathbf{wp}[P_1](f) = [\varphi_1] \cdot \underbrace{\left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_1} p_{1,j} \cdot f[x_1 \mapsto a_{1,j}] \right)}_{=h} + [\neg\varphi_1] \cdot \underbrace{f}_{=g}. \quad (\text{By Equation 7.I})$$

Inductive step. Assume the lemma holds for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ as induction hypothesis. We need to show that Equation 7.II holds for $P = P_{n+1}; P_1; \dots; P_n$ and all $1 \leq i \leq n+1$. Case $i = n+1$ is equivalent to the base case. For $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{wp}[P](f) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_{n+1}; P_1; \dots; P_n](f) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_{n+1}](\text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](f)) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_{n+1}]([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \quad (\text{By I.H., } h \in \mathbb{E}_{\setminus x_i}) \\
&= [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g)[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) \quad (\text{By Equation 7.I}) \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \\
&= [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}]) \right) \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \quad (x_{n+1} \text{ does not occur in } \varphi_i) \\
&= [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot [\varphi_i] \cdot h[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \quad (\text{Multiply out, pull apart sum}) \\
&= [\varphi_i] \cdot [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot h[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot g[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \quad (\text{Multiply out}) \\
&= [\varphi_i] \cdot [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot h[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot [\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot g[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) \\
&\quad + [\varphi_i] \cdot [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot h \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot g \quad (\text{Multiply out}) \\
&= [\varphi_i] \cdot \underbrace{\left([\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot h[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) + [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot h \right)}_{=h' \in \mathbb{E}_{\setminus x_i}} \\
&\quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot \underbrace{\left([\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_{n+1}} p_{n+1,j} \cdot g[x_{n+1} \mapsto a_{n+1,j}] \right) + [\neg\varphi_{n+1}] \cdot g \right)}_{=g' \in \mathbb{E}}.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 7.5. For all $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$, all $f, u \in \mathbb{E}$ and all $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have

$$\text{wp}[P_i](u \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) = \text{wp}[P_i](u) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) .$$

Proof. By Lemma 7.4, there exist expectations $g \in \mathbb{E}$ and $h \in \mathbb{E}_{\setminus x_i}$ such that

$$\text{wp}[P](f) = [\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g \quad (7.111)$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq n$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{wp}[P_i](u \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_i](u \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g)) && \text{(By Equation 7.111)} \\ &= [\varphi_i] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot (u \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g))[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \right) && \text{(By Equation 7.1)} \\ & \quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot u \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \\ &= [\varphi_i] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot u[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}]) \right) && (x_i \text{ does not occur in } h \text{ and } \varphi_i) \\ & \quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot u \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \\ &= [\varphi_i] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot u[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \cdot h \right) && ([\varphi_i] \cdot [\neg\varphi_i] = \mathbf{0}, [\varphi_i] \cdot [\varphi_i] = [\varphi_i]) \\ & \quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot u \cdot ([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g) \\ &= [\varphi_i] \cdot h \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot u[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \right) && ([\neg\varphi_i] \cdot [\neg\varphi_i] = [\neg\varphi_i]) \\ & \quad + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot u \cdot g \\ &= \underbrace{\left([\varphi_i] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot u[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \right) \right)}_{=\text{wp}[P_i](u)} + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot u \cdot \underbrace{([\varphi_i] \cdot h + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot g)}_{=\text{wp}[P](f)} && ([\varphi_i] \cdot [\neg\varphi_i] = \mathbf{0}) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_i](u) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) . && \text{(By Equation 7.111)} \end{aligned}$$

□

We are now in a position to show that every loop in $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ fulfils the i.i.d. property. We do so by proving a stronger statement: For all $f, g \in \mathbb{E}$ and all $P \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$, we have

$$\text{wp}[P](g \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) = \text{wp}[P](g) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) .$$

The i.i.d. property then follows by instantiating g with the loop guard φ .

Lemma 7.6. For all $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$ and all $f, g \in \mathbb{E}$, we have

$$\text{wp}[P](g \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) = \text{wp}[P](g) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) .$$

Proof. By induction on n .

Base case. The base case, i.e. $n = 1$, follows from Lemma 7.5.

Inductive step. Assume the lemma holds for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ as induction hypothesis. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](g \cdot \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](g \cdot \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f))) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](g) \cdot \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f)) && \text{(By Lemma 7.5)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n] (\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](g) \cdot \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n] (\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](f))) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n] (\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](g)) \cdot \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n] (\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](f)) \quad (\text{By I.H.}) \\
&= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](g) \cdot \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f) .
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

After verifying that every loop in $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ fulfils the i.i.d. property, we prove the validity of the second and third statement of Theorem 7.3.

Proof of 2. As every $P \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$ is loop-free by definition and every loop-free program terminates almost-surely on each initial state, $\text{wp}[P](\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$ follows immediately.

Proof of 3. We have to show

$$\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})$$

for all $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$. We proceed as follows: We first show that none of the variables x_1, \dots, x_n occur in $\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\mathbf{0})$ (Lemma 7.7). Afterwards, we observe that if none of the variables x_1, \dots, x_n occur in $f \in \mathbb{E}$, then $\text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](f) = f$ (Lemma 7.8). Combining these two results implies the desired result. Towards this end, observe

$$\text{ert}[P_i](f) = \mathbf{1} + [\varphi_i] \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} + \sum_{j=1}^{m_i} p_{i,j} \cdot f[x_i \mapsto a_{i,j}] \right) + [\neg\varphi_i] \cdot f \quad (7.4V)$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq n$ and all $f \in \mathbb{T}$.

Lemma 7.7. *Let $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$. None of the variables x_1, \dots, x_n occur in $\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\mathbf{0})$.*

Proof. We prove a stronger statement, i.e. if none of the variables x_1, \dots, x_n occur in $f \in \mathbb{T}$, then they do not occur in $\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](f)$, as well. The lemma follows by instantiating f with $\mathbf{0}$. We proceed by induction on n .

Base case. The base case follows from Equation 7.4V and the definition of $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$.

Inductive case. Assume the lemma holds for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ as induction hypothesis. We have

$$\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f) = \text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n] \left(\underbrace{\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f)}_{x_1, \dots, x_{n+1} \text{ do not occur}} \right).$$

The fact that x_{n+1} does not occur in $\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f)$ follows from Equation 7.4V. As x_1, \dots, x_n do not occur in $\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f)$, it follows by induction hypothesis that x_1, \dots, x_n do not occur in $\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f)) = \text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f)$, as well. \square

Lemma 7.8. *Let $P = P_1; \dots; P_n \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}^{\text{loop}}$. If x_1, \dots, x_n do not occur in $f \in \mathbb{E}$, then*

$$\text{wp}[P](f) = f .$$

Proof. By induction on n .

Base case. For $n = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{wp}[P_1](f) &= [\varphi_1] \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{m_1} p_{1,j} \cdot f[x_1 \mapsto a_{1,j}] \right) + [\neg\varphi_1] \cdot f \quad (\text{By Equation 7.I}) \\
&= [\varphi_1] \cdot f + [\neg\varphi_1] \cdot f \quad (x_1 \text{ does not occur in } f) \\
&= f . \quad ([\varphi_1] + [\neg\varphi_1] = \mathbf{1})
\end{aligned}$$

Inductive case. Assume the lemma holds for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ as induction hypothesis. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f) &= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\text{wp}[P_{n+1}](f)) \\ &= \text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](f) && \text{(See base case)} \\ &= f. && \text{(By I.H.)} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

As x_1, \dots, x_n do not occur in $\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\mathbf{0})$ (Lemma 7.7), Lemma 7.8 yields $\text{wp}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P_1; \dots; P_n](\mathbf{0})$. This completes the proof of Theorem 7.3.

Finally, we are in a position to prove the following theorem.

Theorem 7.9. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a Bayesian Network with corresponding conditional probability distributions CPD_v for all $v \in V$. The expected simulation time of G is a computable function given by $\text{ert}[\text{BP}_G](\mathbf{0})$.*

Proof. We prove that $\text{ert}[\text{BP}_G](f)$ is a computable function for all computable $f \in \mathbb{T}$. The theorem then follows by instantiating f with $\mathbf{0}$. First observe that $\text{BP}_G = \text{empty}; P_1; \dots; P_n \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$, where each P_i is either a conditional probabilistic assignment or a loop in $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$. Hence, we have to show that $\text{ert}[\text{empty}; P_1; \dots; P_n](f)$ is a computable function. We proceed by induction on n .

Base case. As $\text{ert}[\text{empty}](f) = f$, function $\text{ert}[\text{empty}](f)$ is computable.

Inductive case. We have to show that

$\text{ert}[\text{empty}; P_1; \dots; P_n; P_{n+1}](f) = \text{ert}[\text{empty}; P_1; \dots; P_n](\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f))$ is a computable function for all computable $f \in \mathbb{T}$. By induction hypothesis, $\text{ert}[\text{empty}; P_1; \dots; P_n](g)$ is a computable function for all computable $g \in \mathbb{T}$. Therefore, it suffices to prove that $\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f)$ is computable for all computable $f \in \mathbb{T}$, where P_{n+1} is either a conditional probabilistic assignment or a loop in $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$. If P_{n+1} is a conditional probabilistic assignment, then $\text{ert}[P_{n+1}](f)$ is given by Equation 7.IV and hence computable. If $P_{n+1} = \text{while}(\varphi)\{P'\} \in \text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$, then Theorem 7.3 implies that the loop fulfils all three premises of Theorem 6.1. Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P'\}](f) \\ &= \mathbf{1} + \frac{[\varphi]}{\mathbf{1} - \text{wp}[P']([\varphi])} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P'](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P']([\neg\varphi] \cdot f)) + [\neg\varphi] \cdot f. \end{aligned}$$

Since P' is loop-free by definition, $\text{wp}[P']([\varphi])$, $\text{ert}[P'](\mathbf{0})$ and $\text{wp}[P']([\neg\varphi] \cdot f)$ are computable and hence $\text{ert}[\text{while}(\varphi)\{P'\}](f)$ is computable. \square

The following example demonstrates the computation of the expected simulation time of a given Bayesian Network.

Example 7.10. Consider the Bayesian Network G shown in Figure 7.1. We abbreviate the nodes by their first letters d, i, g and m . Furthermore, we want to condition the value of program variable x_g corresponding to node g to 1, i.e. $\text{Cond}(x_g) = \{x_g = 1\}$. Then the following program BP_G simulates the network:

```

1   $x_d := 0.6 \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + 0.4 \cdot \langle 1 \rangle;$ 
2   $x_i := 0.7 \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + 0.3 \cdot \langle 1 \rangle;$ 

3   $x_g := \diamond;$ 
4  while( $x_g \neq 1$ ) {
5    if( $x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 0$ ) {
6       $x_g := 0.95 \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + 0.05 \cdot \langle 1 \rangle;$ 
7    }
8    if( $x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 1$ ) {
9       $x_g := 0.05 \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + 0.95 \cdot \langle 1 \rangle;$ 
10   }
11   if( $x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 1$ ) {
12      $x_g := 0.5 \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + 0.5 \cdot \langle 1 \rangle;$ 
13   }
14   if( $x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 0$ ) {
15      $x_g := 0.6 \cdot \langle 0 \rangle + 0.4 \cdot \langle 1 \rangle;$ 
16   }
17 };
```

Let P_i denote the conditional probabilistic assignment in line i for $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 14, 16\}$, P_{loop} denote the loop beginning in line 4 and P_{body} its body. We have to compute $\text{ert}[P_1; P_2; P_3; P_{\text{loop}}; P_{14}; P_{16}](\mathbf{0})$. We have

$$\text{ert}[P_{14}; P_{16}](\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{2} + [x_g = 0] + [x_g = 1]. \quad (7.V)$$

By applying Theorem 7.3 and Theorem 6.1, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](f) \\ &= \mathbf{1} + \frac{[x_g \neq 1]}{\mathbf{1} - \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([x_g \neq 1])} \cdot (\mathbf{1} + \text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{0}) + \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([x_g = 1] \cdot f)) + [x_g = 1] \cdot f \end{aligned} \quad (7.VI)$$

as the expected run-time of loop P_{loop} w.r.t. to continuation $f \in \mathbb{T}$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([x_g \neq 1]) &= [x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 0] \cdot 0.95 + [x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 1] \cdot 0.05 \\ &\quad + [x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 1] \cdot 0.5 + [x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 0] \cdot 0.6, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{wp}[P_{\text{body}}]([x_g = 1] \cdot f) \\ &= [x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 0] \cdot 0.05 \cdot f[x_g \mapsto 1] + [x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 1] \cdot 0.95 \cdot f[x_g \mapsto 1] \\ &\quad + [x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 1] \cdot 0.5 \cdot f[x_g \mapsto 1] + [x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 0] \cdot 0.4 \cdot f[x_g \mapsto 1], \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{ert}[P_{\text{body}}](\mathbf{0}) \\ &= \mathbf{4} + [x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 0] + [x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 1] + [x_d = 0 \wedge x_i = 1] + [x_d = 1 \wedge x_i = 0]. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ert}[P_1; P_2; P_3](g) &= \mathbf{3} + 0.42 \cdot g[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 0, x_d \mapsto 0] + 0.18 \cdot g[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 1, x_d \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + 0.28 \cdot g[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 0, x_d \mapsto 1] + 0.12 \cdot g[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 1, x_d \mapsto 1] . \end{aligned} \tag{7.VII}$$

Overall, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{ert}[P_1; P_2; P_3; P_{\text{loop}}; P_{14}; P_{16}](\mathbf{0}) \\ &= \text{ert}[P_1; P_2; P_3](\text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](\text{ert}[P_{14}; P_{16}](\mathbf{0}))) \\ &= \text{ert}[P_1; P_2; P_3](\text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](\mathbf{2} + [x_g = 0] + [x_g = 1])) \quad (\text{By Equation 7.V}) \\ &= \mathbf{3} + 0.42 \cdot \text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](\mathbf{2} + [x_g = 0] + [x_g = 1])[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 0, x_d \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + 0.18 \cdot \text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](\mathbf{2} + [x_g = 0] + [x_g = 1])[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 1, x_d \mapsto 0] \\ &\quad + 0.28 \cdot \text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](\mathbf{2} + [x_g = 0] + [x_g = 1])[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 0, x_d \mapsto 1] \\ &\quad + 0.12 \cdot \text{ert}[P_{\text{loop}}](\mathbf{2} + [x_g = 0] + [x_g = 1])[x_g \mapsto \diamond, x_i \mapsto 1, x_d \mapsto 1] \\ &\quad \quad \quad (\text{By Equation 7.VII}) \\ &\approx \mathbf{3} + 0.42 \cdot \mathbf{181} + 0.18 \cdot \mathbf{19} + 0.28 \cdot \mathbf{23.5} + 0.12 \cdot \mathbf{10.47} \quad (\text{By Equation 7.VI}) \\ &= 90.2764 . \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the Bayesian Network with condition $x_g = 1$ has an expected simulation time of 90.2764 units of time, i.e. we need 90.2764 guard evaluations and assignments on average until all conditions are satisfied and all values are sampled. ■

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Future Work

In this thesis, we studied independent and identically distributed loops and their expected run-times. Using weakest pre-expectation semantics and a calculus for reasoning about expected run-times of probabilistic programs, we derived a proof rule for expected run-times of i.i.d. loops. The proof rule can reduce the effort of determining expected run-times of these loops to syntactic reasoning. Hence, it offers a technique to compute expected run-times of i.i.d. loops satisfying the premises automatically.

Furthermore, we introduced Bayesian Networks and formally defined how to simulate them by means of probabilistic programs. In particular, we used independent and identically distributed loops to simulate conditioning. Finally, we proved that the proof rule can be applied to automatically compute the expected simulation time of Bayesian Networks and demonstrated the computation by means of an example.

Future Work In order to apply the proof rule presented in Chapter 6 to a given loop $\text{while}(\varphi)\{P\}$, one needs to verify three properties. In particular, one needs to verify whether the loop is i.i.d., i.e. whether

$$\text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) = \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)$$

for all $f \in \mathbb{E}$. This condition can possibly be weakened. It might suffice to only consider certain post-expectations rather than all post-expectations.

Another property one has to verify is that the loop has the same expected run-time on each iteration, i.e.

$$\text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) = \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}).$$

We suspect that this property is implied by the i.i.d. property, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \forall f \in \mathbb{E} : \text{wp}[P]([\varphi] \cdot \text{wp}[P](f)) &= \text{wp}[P]([\varphi]) \cdot \text{wp}[P](f) \\ \implies \text{wp}[P](\text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0})) &= \text{ert}[P](\mathbf{0}). \end{aligned}$$

The proof of this conjecture remains open.

The fragment $\text{pProgs}_{\text{frag}}$ defined in Section 7.2 was designed for the purpose of proving that the expected simulation time of a Bayesian Network is a computable function, but it is far from being maximal. That is to say, one could ask whether it can be extended to a larger class of programs while preserving the property that every loop in that fragment fulfils all premises of the proof rule.

Moreover, the results presented in Chapter 7 can be implemented. They provide the theoretical foundations for a tool taking a Bayesian Network and conditions over the associated random variables as input, translates this network to a probabilistic program and returns the network's expected simulation time.

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